

Self-Made Algebraic Magic, Semi-Magic and Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 8

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The whole work as pdf files is available at author's sites:

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16282>

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=16523>

This work is without use of any kind of programming language

Abstract

*This work brings **magic**, **semi-magic** and **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 8 for **reduced entries**. By **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less number of entries. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more sequential numbers. These **entries** are **non-sequential positive and negative numbers**. Sometimes, we call these kind of magic squares as **self-made**. It means that these are complete in themselves. Just put the values of entries and choose the magic sum, we get a magic square. In some cases, there maybe **decimal** or **fractional** values of entries depending on the types of magic squares. Different kind of magic squares are used to bring these **self-made** magic squares. These are of type, **block-wise**, **cornered**, **single-digit bordered**, **double-digit bordered**, etc. In some cases, the idea of **magic rectangles** is also applied. In each case, these are considered with **equal width and length**. There are total 26 results. Out of them, 8 are of magic squares, 5 are of **semi-magic** squares and 13 are of **pandiagonal** magic squares. For the previous work readers are suggested to see author's work [30]-[41].*

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1 Introduction

This work brings **self-made algebraic pandiagonal** magic squares of order 8. By **self-made** or **reduced** or **less entries**, we understand that instead of normal n^2 entries of a magic square order n , we are using less numbers of entries, where the magic square is complete in itself. Putting any integer values for these less entries, we shall get always a magic square. Moreover, in these situations the entries are no more **sequential** numbers. These entries are **non-sequential positive** and/or **negative** numbers. In some cases, these may be **decimal** or **fractional** values depending on the way of choosing the entries. Sometime to avoid **decimal** or **fractional** entries we apply certain conditions. These conditions depends on the types of magic squares. The name **self-made** is not known in the literature of magic squares. It is being introduced for first time. The work is based on different types of magic squares, such as, **pandiagonal, block-wise, cornered, single-digit bordered, double-digit bordered**, etc. It is not necessary, but we worked with **magic rectangles** having equal width and length for the same category within a magic square. If we relax this condition, i.e., by considering only equality of width, still we have good results. For more details refer author's previous works. In this work, we brought total 26 magic squares, out of them 8 are just magic squares, 5 are **semi-magic** and 13 are **pandiagonal** magic squares. This work is also available online at the links given above. The table below give the number of **self-made algebraic** magic squares of order 8. For more details refer author's work [36]-[43].

Order	Magic Squares	Semi-Magic Squares	Pandiagonal Magic Squares	Total
8	8	5	13	26

The author [30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35] also worked on similar kind of work but from different point of view. This work is for the magic squares of orders 3 to 12 for the **dates** and **days** of the year 2025, where the **dates** are few entries and **days** are the sums of the magic squares. This work is revised and enlarged version of author's previous works [31, 37, 40].

2 Magic Squares of Order 8

Below are five examples of magic squares of order 8. These are **pandiagonal**, **striped**, **cornered**, **single-digit bordered** and **double-digit bordered** magic squares. All the four examples are for the **sequential entries** from 1 to 64.

Example 2.1. Let's consider following five magic squares of order 8 for the sequential entries from 1 to 64

	pan	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
260	7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54	260	
260	2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51	260	
260	64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13	260	
260	57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12	260	
260	23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38	260	
260	18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35	260	
260	48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29	260	
260	41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28	260	
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

mgc									260
31	36	25	38	43	22	13	52	260	
26	37	32	35	23	42	1	64	260	
40	27	34	29	41	24	54	11	260	
33	30	39	28	49	16	9	56	260	
18	17	44	50	20	46	7	58	260	
47	48	21	15	19	45	53	12	260	
10	8	62	51	6	61	60	2	260	
55	57	3	14	59	4	63	5	260	
260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	

mgc									260
8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7	260	
5	46	44	17	50	18	20	60	260	
6	16	31	36	25	38	49	59	260	
11	22	26	37	32	35	43	54	260	
61	24	40	27	34	29	41	4	260	
56	42	33	30	39	28	23	9	260	
55	45	21	48	15	47	19	10	260	
58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57	260	
260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	

mgc									260
3	1	63	61	60	58	8	6	260	
62	64	2	4	5	7	57	59	260	
17	48	31	36	25	38	21	44	260	
20	45	26	37	32	35	24	41	260	
47	18	40	27	34	29	43	22	260	
46	19	33	30	39	28	42	23	260	
53	55	9	11	16	14	50	52	260	
12	10	56	54	49	51	15	13	260	
260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	

mgc									260
12	54	55	9	8	58	59	5	260	
53	11	10	56	57	7	6	60	260	
1	63	62	4	13	51	50	16	260	
64	2	3	61	52	14	15	49	260	
25	39	38	28	24	42	43	21	260	
40	26	27	37	41	23	22	44	260	
20	46	47	17	29	35	34	32	260	
45	19	18	48	36	30	31	33	260	
260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	

• Details

The first magic square is **pandiagonal** with four equal sum **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. The second magic square **cornered** magic square. The third magic square is **single-digit bordered** magic squares. The

*fourth magic square is **double-digit bordered** magic square. The internal magic squares are of orders 4 and 6. In case of forth example, there is only one internal magic square of order 4. The fifth example is **striped** magic square of order 8. More details on different kinds of magic squares of order 8 refer author's work [11, 16, 25, 27].*

Based on above magic squares we shall construct **reduced entries pandiagonal** magic squares of order 8.

3 Self-Made Magic Squares of Order 8

Below are few results on magic squares of reduced entries constructed based on the Example 5.1.

3.1 Four Equal Sums Magic Squares of Order 4

Result 3.1. *Let's consider a following magic squares of order 8 with reduced entries:*

A1	A2	M-A1-A6-A2	A6	A8	A9	M-A8-A13-A9	A13
A3	A4	A7	M-A4-A7-A3	A10	A11	A14	M-A11-A14-A10
A5+A6-A3	A1+A5-A7	M-A1-A5-A4	A4+A7+A3-A5-A6	A12+A13-A10	A8+A12-A14	M-A8-A12-A11	A11+A14+A10-A12-A13
M-A1-A5-A6	M-A1-A5-A4+A7-A2	2*A1+A5+A6+A4-A7+A2-M	A5	M-A8-A12-A13	M-A8-A12-A11+A14-A9	2*A8+A12+A13+A11-A14+A9-M	A12
A15	A16	M-A15-A20-A16	A20	A22	A23	M-A22-A27-A23	A27
A17	A18	A21	M-A18-A21-A17	A24	A25	A28	M-A25-A28-A24
A19+A20-A17	A15+A19-A21	M-A15-A19-A18	A18+A21+A17-A19-A20	A26+A27-A24	A22+A26-A28	M-A22-A26-A25	A25+A28+A24-A26-A27
M-A15-A19-A20	M-A15-A19-A18+A21-A16	2*A15+A19+A20+A18-A21+A16-M	A19	M-A22-A26-A27	M-A22-A26-A25+A28-A23	2*A22+A26+A27+A25-A28+A23-M	A26

Details:

It is a magic square of order 8 composed with four equal sums magic squares of order 4. The letters M and T represents the magic squares of orders 4 and 8 respectively. In this case we have $T = 2 \times M$, where M is the magic sum of order 4. In this case what ever integer value of M we choose, the magic sum is always an even numbers. See below two examples.

Example 3.1. Let's consider following two examples:

8x8	mgc									166
	10	13	35	25	31	34	-28	46	166	
	16	19	28	20	37	40	49	-43	166	
	31	4	32	16	52	25	-31	37	166	
	26	47	-12	22	-37	-16	93	43	166	
	52	55	-91	67	73	76	-154	88	166	
	58	61	70	-106	79	82	91	-169	166	
	73	46	-94	58	94	67	-157	79	166	
	-100	-79	198	64	-163	-142	303	85	166	
	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	166	

8x8	mgc									142
	10	13	23	25	31	34	-40	46	142	
	16	19	28	8	37	40	49	-55	142	
	31	4	20	16	52	25	-43	37	142	
	14	35	0	22	-49	-28	105	43	142	
	52	55	-103	67	73	76	-166	88	142	
	58	61	70	-118	79	82	91	-181	142	
	73	46	-106	58	94	67	-169	79	142	
	-112	-91	210	64	-175	-154	315	85	142	
	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	142	

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 83$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 166$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 71$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 142$$

3.2 Self-Made Striped Magic Square of Order 8

By striped magic squares we understand that the magic constructed only with equal width **magic rectangles**. For more details see the author's work [27]. The result below give reduced entries striped magic square of order 8. It also included magic squares of order 4.

Result 3.2. *Let's consider following striped square of order 8 with reduced entries:*

$A1-A3-A5-A6-A8+A7$	$A6+A8-2*m+A11+A1-A3-A5$	$2*m$	$2*m+2*A3+2*A5-A7-A11-2*A1$	$A5+2*A3-A7-A11+A10-A9$	$2*m-A9-A5-A10$	$A9-2*A3+A7+A11$	$A9$
$m+A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-A1$	$3*m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11-A1$	$(-m)$	$A7-m+A11+2*A1-2*A3-2*A5$	$m+A9-A10+A11-A5-2*A3+A7$	$A9+A5+A10-m$	$m-A9+2*A3-A7-A11$	$m-A9$
$2*A3+2*A5-A7-A11-A1$	$A1$	$A6+A8+A11-A3-A5$	$2*m+A7-A3-A5-A6-A8$	$A5+2*A3-A7-A11$	$A5$	$2*m+A7+A11-A10-2*A3-2*A5$	$A10$
$A1+m-2*A3-2*A5+A7+A11$	$m-A1$	$m+A3+A5-A6-A8-A11$	$A3+A5+A6+A8-A7-m$	$m+A7+A11-A5-2*A3$	$m-A5$	$2*A3+2*A5-A7-A11+A10-m$	$m-A10$
$A3+A2-A7-A11+A4$	$2*m-A3-A2-A4$	$A7+A11-A3$	$A3$	$2*m-A6-A8-A11$	$A6+A8-A7$	$A7$	$A11$
$m+A7+A11-A4-A3-A2$	$A3+A2+A4-m$	$m+A3-A7-A11$	$m-A3$	$A6+A8+A11-m$	$m+A7-A6-A8$	$m-A7$	$m-A11$
$A2+2*A3-A7-A11$	$A2$	$2*m+A7+A11-2*A2-A4-2*A3$	$A4$	$A6+A11-A7$	$A6$	$A8$	$2*m+A7-2*A6-A8-A11$
$m+A7+A11-A2-2*A3$	$m-A2$	$2*A3-A7-A11+2*A2+A4-m$	$m-A4$	$m+A7-A11-A6$	$m-A6$	$m-A8$	$2*A6+A8+A11-A7-m$

Details:

It is a **striped** magic square of order 8 where the magic rectangles of order 2×4 are of equal width and length, i.e., $m \times 2m$. In this case the magic sum is $T = m \times 2m$. It includes five magic squares of order 4 also. These are specified in an example.

Example 3.2. *Let's consider following example:*

3.3 Self-Made Double-Digit Bordered Magic Square of Order 8

Result 3.3. *Let's consider a following magic squares of order 8 with reduced entries:*

A18	A19	$2*(T-M)/2-A15-A16-A17$	A15	A16	A17	$2*M-T+A18-A19+A23$	$T-M-A23-2*A18$
$2*A13+A24+A14+2*A18-T+M-A19$	$T-M-2*A18-A13$	$A15+A16+A17-(T-M)/2$	$(T-M)/2-A15$	$(T-M)/2-A16$	$(T-M)/2-A17$	$T-M-A23-A13-A24-A18+A19$	$2*M-T+A18+A23-A14$
$T-M-A7-A8-A9$	$A7+A8+A9-(T-M)/2$	A1	$M+A4-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$A10+A11+A12-(T-M)/2$	$T-M-A10-A11-A12$
A7	$(T-M)/2-A7$	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	$(T-M)/2-A10$	A10
A8	$(T-M)/2-A8$	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	$(T-M)/2-A11$	A11
A9	$(T-M)/2-A9$	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	$(T-M)/2-A12$	A12
$T-2*A13-A14+A19-3*A18-A23-A24$	$A23+3*A18+A24-A19+A13-T+M$	$A20+A21+A22-(T-M)/2$	$(T-M)/2-A20$	$(T-M)/2-A21$	$(T-M)/2-A22$	A13	A14
A23	$M-A23-A18-A24$	$T-M-A20-A21-A22$	A20	A21	A22	A24	A18

Details:

*It is a **double-digit bordered** magic square of order 8 embedded a magic square of order 4. The four magic rectangles of orders 2×4 are of equal width and length. The letters M and T represents the magic squares of orders 4 and 8 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums M and T should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd** numbers.*

Example 3.3. *Let's consider following two examples:*

1a	mgc									200	1b	mgc									221
	45	47	-43	39	41	43	93	-65	200		45	47	-43	39	41	43	114	-65	221		
	127	-45	83	1	-1	-3	-65	103	200		127	-45	83	1	-1	-3	-65	124	221		
	5	35	11	105	-11	15	53	-13	200		5	35	11	126	-11	15	53	-13	221		
	23	17	21	17	19	63	11	29	200		23	17	21	17	19	84	11	29	221		
	25	15	7	5	79	29	9	31	200		25	15	7	5	100	29	9	31	221		
	27	13	81	-7	33	13	7	33	200		27	13	102	-7	33	13	7	33	221		
	-107	155	113	-9	-11	-13	35	37	200		-86	155	113	-9	-11	-13	35	37	221		
	55	-37	-73	49	51	53	57	45	200		55	-16	-73	49	51	53	57	45	221		
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200		221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221	221		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 120$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 200$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 141$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 221$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 40 \times 80$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 40 \times 80.$$

3.4 Self-Made Cornered Magic Squares of Order 8

Result 3.4. *Let's consider following cornered magic squares of order 8 with reduced entries:*

A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	S-M-A10	A10	a18	T-S-A18
A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	S-M-A11	A11	a19	T-S-A19
A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	M-S+A10 +A11+A12	2*(S-M)- A10-A11-A12	A20	T-S-A20
M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3 +2*A4-A5-A6	A2	S-M-A12	A12	3*(T-S)-A18-A19- A20-A21-A22	2*(S-T)+A18+A19 +A20+A21+A22
2*S-3*M+A1- A8+3*A4- A11+A10	S-M-A8	3*M-2*S-A1 +2*A8-3*A4 +A11-A10+A9	S-M-A9	(S-M)/2	(5*M-3*S)/2	A21	T-S-A21
2*M-S-A1+ A8-3*A4+ A11-A10	A8	3*S-4*M+A1- 2*A8+3*A4- A11+A10-A9	A9	(5*M-3*S)/2	(S-M)/2	A22	T-S-A22
A14	2*A11-T-5*S-A1 +2*A9+2*A8+2*A12+A 14-3*A4+A18-A19+8*M	A15	4*T+2*S-2*A14+A1- 2*A11-2*A9-2*A8- 2*A12+3*A4-A18+A19- 8*M-A15-A16-A17	A16	A17	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2
T-S-A14	2*T+4*S+A1-2*A11- 2*A9-2*A8-2*A12- A14+3*A4-A18+A19- 8*M	T-S-A15	2*A14-3*S-3*T-A1 +2*A11+2*A9+2*A8 +2*A12-3*A4+A18-A19 +8*M+A15+A16+A17	T-S-A16	T-S-A17	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2

Details:

It is a *cornered* magic square of order. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal width and length in each case. The letters M, S and T represents the magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums M, S and T should be of same type, i.e., either *even* or *odd* numbers.

Example 3.4. *Let's consider following two examples:*

2a	mgc									220	2b	mgc									235
	21	87	-21	23	0	30	43	37	220		21	88	-21	23	10	30	47	37	235		
	26	24	25	35	63	-33	50	30	220		26	24	25	36	53	-13	23	61	235		
	19	18	43	30	-1	31	24	56	220		19	18	44	30	9	31	47	37	235		
	44	-19	63	22	-2	32	42	38	220		45	-19	63	22	8	32	46	38	235		
	2	-74	131	1	15	65	41	39	220		12	-53	110	11	20	51	45	39	235		
	28	104	-101	29	65	15	40	40	220		28	93	-70	29	51	20	44	40	235		
	56	180	-131	46	45	44	40	-60	220		90	201	-186	50	49	48	42	-59	235		
	24	-100	211	34	35	36	-60	40	220		-6	-117	270	34	35	36	-59	42	235		
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		235	235	235	235	235	235	235	235	235		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 110$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 140$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 220$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 111$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 151$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 235$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 30 \times 60$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 80 \times 240$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 4} := 40 \times 80$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 84 \times 252$$

Result 3.5. Let's consider following *cornered* magic squares of order 8 with reduced entries:

$4*S-6*M+A12$	$S+2*A13+2*A14-4*A12-M$	$2*A12+9*M-6*S-A13-A14$	S-A13-M	S-A14-M	A12	T-S-A16	A16
$4*M-3*S+A9+A10+A11$	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	$4*S-A9-A10-A11-5*M$	$T-S-A16-A1-A13-A9-A14+2*A12-7*S-3*A4+10*M$	$A16+A1+A13+A9+A14-2*A12+7*S+3*A4-10*M$
S-A9-M	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	A9	$2*A16+A18+A19+A1-2*T+9*S+A13+A9+A14-2*A12+3*A4-10*M+A17$	$3*T-10*S-A18-A19-2*A16-A1-A13-A9-A14+2*A12-3*A4+10*M-A17$
S-A10-M	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	A10	T-S-A17	A17
S-A11-M	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	A11	T-S-A18	A18
$5*M-A12-3*S$	$4*A12-2*A13-2*A14$	$7*S+A13+A14-2*A12-10*M$	A13	A14	$5*M-A12-3*S$	T-S-A19	A19
$T-S+A13+A9+A14-2*A12+2*A1+7*S+6*A4-11*M$	$8*S+A13+A9+A14-2*A12+2*A1+6*A4-11*M$	$A21+A20+A22-T-2*A13-2*A9-2*A14+4*A12-4*A1-14*S-12*A4+22*M$	T-S-A20	T-S-A21	T-S-A22	$(T-S)/2$	$(7*S-5*T)/2$
$11*M-A13-A9-A14+2*A12-2*A1-7*S-6*A4$	$T-9*S-A13-A9-A14+2*A12-2*A1-6*A4+11*M$	$2*T+13*S+2*A13+2*A9+2*A14-4*A12+4*A1+12*A4-22*M-A21-A20-A22$	A20	A21	A22	$(7*S-5*T)/2$	$(T-S)/2$

Details:

It is a *cornered* magic square of order 8 embedded with a *single-digit bordered* magic square of order 6. It has a magic square of order 4 as an inner part. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 are of equal width and length. The letters M, S and T represent the magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums M, S and T should be of the same type, i.e., either *even* or *odd* numbers.

Example 3.5. Let's consider following two examples:

3a	mgc								230	3b	mgc								231
	24	68	21	3	0	44	14	56	230		28	69	15	4	1	44	14	56	231
	74	11	93	-11	17	-24	-121	191	230		71	11	93	-11	17	-20	-128	198	231
	15	26	20	23	41	35	293	-223	230		16	26	20	23	41	35	300	-230	231
	12	5	2	65	38	38	11	59	230		13	5	2	65	38	38	11	59	231
	9	68	-5	33	14	41	8	62	230		10	68	-5	33	14	41	8	62	231
	26	-18	29	47	50	26	5	65	230		23	-18	36	47	50	23	5	65	231
	166	256	-209	2	-1	-4	35	-15	230		173	264	-224	2	-1	-4	35	-14	231
	-96	-186	279	68	71	74	-15	35	230		-103	-194	294	68	71	74	-14	35	231
	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230	230		231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231	231

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 110$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 160$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 230$$

Second Example

$$M_{4 \times 4} := 110$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 161$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 231$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 70 \times 210$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 70 \times 210$$

Result 3.6. *Let's consider following cornered magic squares of order 8 with reduced entries:*

$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}-A_{15}$	A4	A7	A11	A15	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}$	T-S-A29	A29
$S-A_{12}-A_5-A_8-A_{16}-A_{19}$	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	T-S-A30	A30
$A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_1-A_2-A_3+A_5+A_8+A_{12}+A_{16}$	$S-A_4-A_5-A_{12}+A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}-A_{17}-A_7-A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_9-A_{11}+A_1+A_2+A_3$	A9	A13	A17	A20	T-S-A31	A31
A1	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_1-A_{18}-A_{14}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}$	$A_{21}+A_{22}+A_{23}+A_{20}-A_{16}-A_{13}-A_6+A_{19}-A_3$	A14	A18	A21	T-S-A32	A32
A2	A6	$S+A_{16}+A_{13}-A_9+A_6-A_{19}+A_3-A_{10}-A_{21}-A_{22}-A_{23}-A_{20}-A_7-A_8$	$A_5+A_{14}+A_{10}+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+2*A_{20}-A_4+A_8-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{13}+2*A_9-2*A_6+2*A_{19}-A_{11}-A_2-A_3-S$	$S-A_{19}-A_{20}-A_{21}-A_{22}-2*A_{23}+A_4+A_7+A_{11}+A_{15}-A_5-A_9-A_{14}$	A22	T-S-A33	A33
A3	$A_{12}+A_{18}+A_{14}+A_{21}+A_{20}+A_{17}+A_7+A_8+A_{15}+A_9-2*A_6+A_{19}+A_{11}-A_2-2*A_3-S$	A10	$2*S+A_4-A_8+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_9+2*A_6-2*A_{19}+A_2+A_3-A_{12}-A_5-2*A_{14}-A_{10}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-2*A_{20}$	$A_{19}+A_{20}+A_{21}+A_{22}+2*A_{23}-A_4-A_7-A_{11}+A_5+A_9+A_{14}-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}$	A23	$2*S-2*T+A_{29}+A_{30}+A_{31}+A_{32}+A_{33}$	$3*T-3*S-A_{29}-A_{30}-A_{31}-A_{32}-A_{33}$
T-S-A25	$A_{30}-A_{29}-2*A_9+A_{13}-A_{25}+2*S-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+2*A_6-A_8+A_3$	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A28	$2*A_{25}+A_{28}+A_{27}+A_{26}-A_{30}+A_{29}+2*A_9-A_{13}-T-S+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}-A_2-A_4-A_{11}+A_5-2*A_6+A_8-A_3$	(T-S)/2	(7*S-5*T)/2
A25	$A_{29}-A_{30}+2*A_9-A_{13}+T+A_{25}-A_{11}-3*S+2*A_{21}+A_{22}+3*A_{23}+A_{18}+2*A_{19}+3*A_{20}+A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}+2*A_{10}-A_2-A_4+A_5-2*A_6+A_8-A_3$	A26	A27	A28	$A_{30}-A_{29}-A_{28}-A_{27}-A_{26}-2*A_9+A_{13}+2*T-2*A_{25}-2*A_{21}-A_{22}-3*A_{23}-A_{18}-2*A_{19}-3*A_{20}-A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{10}+A_2+A_4+A_{11}-A_5+2*A_6-A_8+A_3$	(7*S-5*T)/2	(T-S)/2

Details:

It is a **cornered** magic square of order 8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 are of equal width and length. The letters S and T represents the magic squares of orders 6 and 8 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums S and T should be of same type, i.e., either **even** or **odd** numbers.

Example 3.6. *Let's consider following two examples:*

4a	mgc									220	4b	mgc									251
	212	20	29	41	53	-255	28	92	220		212	20	29	41	53	-234	38	92	251		
	-120	23	32	44	56	65	13	107	220		-99	23	32	44	56	65	23	107	251		
	-34	-75	35	47	59	68	253	-133	220		-34	-54	35	47	59	68	233	-103	251		
	11	-303	209	50	62	71	25	95	220		11	-282	209	50	62	71	35	95	251		
	14	26	-243	526	-297	74	22	98	220		14	26	-222	505	-276	74	32	98	251		
	17	409	38	-608	167	77	19	101	220		17	388	38	-566	167	77	29	101	251		
	16	-683	925	37	34	31	60	-200	220		26	-641	873	47	44	41	65	-204	251		
	104	803	-805	83	86	89	-200	60	220		104	771	-743	83	86	89	-204	65	251		
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220		251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251	251		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 100$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 220$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 121$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 251$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 120 \times 360$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 130 \times 390$$

Result 3.7. Let's consider following *cornered* magic squares of order 8 with reduced entries:

A1	M-A1-A2	A2	$4*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-2*A5-2*A4-A6$	$A5+2*A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	A5	T-2*M-A19	A19
$A1+A2+2*A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	$3*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-A1-A3$	M-A2-A3	$2*A5+A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	$3*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-A5-A4$	M-A5-A6	T-2*M-A20	A20
$4*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-2*A1-A2-2*A3$	$2*A1+A2+A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	A3	A4	M-A4-A6	A6	T-2*M-A21	A21
A7	M-A7-A9	A9	A11	M-A11-A13	A13	T-2*M-A22	A22
M-A7-A8	$A7+A8+A9+A10-M$	M-A9-A10	M-A11-A12	$A11+A12+A13+A14-M$	M-A13-A14	T-2*M-A23	A23
A8	M-A8-A10	A10	A12	M-A12-A14	A14	$2*2*M-2*T+A19+A20+A21+A22+A23$	$3*T-3*2*M-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23$
$2*T-4*M+A19-A20+A6-2*A11-A13-A12-A15+A10$	T-2*M-A15	T-2*M-A16	T-2*M-A17	T-2*M-A18	$6*M-A10-A19+A20-A6+2*A11+A13+A12+2*A15+A16+A17+A18-3*T$	$(T-2*M)/2$	$(7*2*M-5*T)/2$
$2*M+A20-A6+2*A11+A13+A12+A15-A10-A19-T$	A15	A16	A17	A18	$A10+A19+4*T-8*M-A20+A6-2*A11-A13-A12-2*A15-A16-A17-A18$	$(7*2*M-5*T)/2$	$(T-2*M)/2$

Details:

It is a *cornered* magic square of order 8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. The magic square of order 6 is composed of four equal sums *semi-magic* squares of order 3. The magic rectangles of orders 2×6 are of equal width and length. The letters T, S and M represents the magic squares of orders 8, 6 and 3 respectively. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sums S and T should be even numbers as $S = 2 \times M$. See below two examples:

Example 3.7. Let's consider following two examples:

8x8	mgc									130	8x8	mgc									140
	11	35	13	-13	53	19	-35	47	130		11	18	13	-81	104	19	9	47	140		
	81	-53	31	55	-15	19	-37	49	130		132	-104	14	106	-66	2	7	49	140		
	-33	77	15	17	21	21	-39	51	130		-101	128	15	17	4	21	5	51	140		
	23	9	27	31	-7	35	-41	53	130		23	-8	27	31	-24	35	3	53	140		
	11	45	3	-5	77	-13	-43	55	130		-6	62	-14	-22	94	-30	1	55	140		
	25	5	29	33	-11	37	231	-219	130		25	-12	29	33	-28	37	143	-87	140		
	-97	-27	-29	-31	-33	253	6	88	130		-9	17	15	13	11	121	28	-56	140		
	109	39	41	43	45	-241	88	6	130		65	39	41	43	45	-65	-56	28	140		
	130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130	130		140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140		

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{3 \times 3} := 59(\text{semi - magic})$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 118$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 130$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 42(\text{semi - magic})$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 84$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 140$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 12 \times 36$$

Second Example

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 560 \times 168$$

Result 3.8. Let's consider following *cornered* magic squares of order 8 with reduced entries:

$A1-A6+A7-A12+A13$	A1	$3*m-2*A1-A2-A3-A4+A6-A7+A12-A13$	A2	A3	A4	$T-3*m-A18$	A18
$m+A6-A7+A12-A13-A1$	m-A1	$2*A1+A2+A3+A4-A6+A7-A12+A13-2*m$	m-A2	m-A3	m-A4	$T-3*m-A19$	A19
A5	$3*m-A5-A6-A7-A8-A9$	A6	A7	A8	A9	$T-3*m-A20$	A20
m-A5	$A5+A6+A7+A8+A9-2*m$	m-A6	m-A7	m-A8	m-A9	$T-3*m-A21$	A21
$A4+A7-A6+A10-A3$	A10	$3*m-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A11-A12-A13$	A11	A12	A13	$T-3*m-A22$	A22
$m-A4-A7+A6-A10+A3$	m-A10	$A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A11+A12+A13-2*m$	m-A11	m-A12	m-A13	$2*3*m-2*T+A18+A19+A20+A21+A22$	$3*T-3*3*m-A18-A19-A20-A21-A22$
$2*T-10*m+A18-A19+A9-A8+2*A11+A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A13-A14+A12$	$T-3*m-A14$	$T-3*m-A15$	$T-3*m-A16$	$T-3*m-A17$	$13*m-A12-A18+A19-A9+A8-2*A11-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A13+2*A14+A15+A16+A17-3*T$	$(T-3*m)/2$	$(7*3*m-5*T)/2$
$7*m+A19-A9+A8-2*A11-A4-A7+A6-2*A10+A3-A13+A14-A12-A18-T$	A14	A15	A16	A17	$A12+A18+4*T-16*m-A19+A9-A8+2*A11+A4+A7-A6+2*A10-A3+A13-2*A14-A15-A16-A17$	$(7*3*m-5*T)/2$	$(T-3*m)/2$

Details:

It is a *cornered* magic square of order 8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is composed of three magic rectangles of order $m \times 3m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangles. The external magic rectangles of order 2×6 are of equal width and length but not necessarily same as of magic square of order 6. The letters S and T represents the magic squares of orders 6 and 8 respectively. See below two examples:

Example 3.8. Let's consider following two examples:

8x8	mgc								140	8x8	mgc								125
	16	10	34	13	16	19	-29	61	140		16	10	25	13	16	19	-35	61	125
	20	26	2	23	20	17	-32	64	140		17	23	8	20	17	14	-38	64	125
	22	-32	25	28	31	34	-35	67	140		22	-41	25	28	31	34	-41	67	125
	14	68	11	8	5	2	-38	70	140		11	74	8	5	2	-1	-44	70	125
	43	37	-101	40	43	46	-41	73	140		43	37	-110	40	43	46	-47	73	125
	-7	-1	137	-4	-7	-10	271	-239	140		-10	-4	143	-7	-10	-13	283	-257	125
	120	-17	-20	-23	-26	62	16	28	140		120	-23	-26	-29	-32	68	13	34	125
	-88	49	52	55	58	-30	28	16	140		-94	49	52	55	58	-42	34	13	125
	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140		125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125	125

The magic sums of above two examples are as follows:

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 108$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 140$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 99$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 125$$

Above two examples are considered with magic sums as **even** and **odd** numbers. The magic rectangles sums are:

First Example

$$MR_{m \times 3m} := 36 \times 108$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 32 \times 96$$

Second Example

$$MR_{m \times 3m} := 33 \times 99$$

$$MR_{2 \times 6} := 26 \times 78$$

4 Self-Made Semi-Magic Squares of Order 8

Below are 2 results for **reduced entries semi-magic** squares based on Examples 5.1.

Result 4.1. *Let's consider following semi-magic square of order 8 with reduced entries:*

T-S-A17	$2*T+3*S+A19-A14-A20$	T-S-A14	$A18+2*A17-7*T+2*S+A16+A15+2*A14+A21+A22+A24+2*A20+A23$	T-S-A15	T-S-A16	T-S-A18	T-A21-A22-A24-A20-A23-A17-A19
T-S-A20	A1	$A4+M-A6-A1$	$A6-A3-A4$	A3	S-M-A10	A10	A20
T-S-A21	A6	A4	A5	$M-A4-A5-A6$	$A10+A11+A12-S+M$	$2*S-2*M-A10-A11-A12$	A21
T-S-A22	$A2+A3-A6$	$A1+A2-A5$	$M-A1-A2-A4$	$A4+A5+A6-A2-A3$	S-M-A11	A11	A22
T-S-A23	$M-A1-A2-A3$	$A5-A2-2*A4+A6$	$A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6$	A2	S-M-A12	A12	A23
T-S-A24	S-M-A8	$2*S-A8-A1-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-M$	$2*A8+A1+A9+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12+M-2*S$	S-M-A9	$(S-M)/2$	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	A24
T-S-A19	A8	$A8+A1+3*A4+2*A10+A11+A12-S$	$3*S-2*A8-A1-A9-3*A4-2*A10-A11-A12-2*M$	A9	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(S-M)/2$	A19
$A17+A19+7*S+A21+A22+A24+A20+A23-6*T$	$A14+A20-T-A19-4*S$	A14	$8*T-A18-2*A17-3*S-A16-A15-2*A14-A21-A22-A24-2*A20-A23$	A15	A16	A18	A17

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic** square of order 8 embedded with **cornered** magic squares of orders 6.

It is **semi-magic** only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need the following condition:

$$S = \frac{3}{4} \times T, \tag{1}$$

where S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 6 and 8 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.1. First example is of **semi-magic** squares and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (1)

Example 4.1. Let's consider a following **semi-magic** square based on the Result 4.1:

1a	semi	S=3*T/4							230
	-3	851	3	-421	1	-1	-5	-215	210
	-9	21	85	-21	25	11	39	59	210
	-11	31	27	29	23	73	-23	61	210
	-13	17	15	39	39	9	41	63	210
	-15	41	-17	63	23	7	43	65	210
	-17	15	-89	161	13	25	35	67	210
	-7	35	139	-111	37	35	25	57	210
	285	-801	47	471	49	51	55	53	210
	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210	210

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 110$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 160$ and $T_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} := 210$. There are two magic rectangles with equal magic sums $MR_{2 \times 4} := 50 \times 100$.

Example 4.2. Let's consider a following magic square with even number magic sum based on the Result 4.1:

1b	mgc	S=3*T/4							240
	7	971	13	-591	11	9	5	-185	240
	1	21	85	-21	25	31	39	59	240
	-1	31	27	29	23	53	17	61	240
	-3	17	15	39	39	29	41	63	240
	-5	41	-17	63	23	27	43	65	240
	-7	35	-49	121	33	35	5	67	240
	3	35	119	-51	37	5	35	57	240
	245	-911	47	651	49	51	55	53	240
	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240	240

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 110$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 180$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 240$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (1), i.e., $T = \frac{3}{4} \times T$. Moreover, the magic rectangles sums is $MR_{2 \times 4} := 70 \times 140$.

Result 4.2. *Let's consider following semi-magic square of order 8 with reduced entries:*

T-S-A27	$2*T+3*S+A17-2*A14-A24-2*A13-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A18-2*A15$	T-S-A24	$A28+2*A27+2*A14-7*T+2*S+A26+A25+2*A24+2*A13+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A19+A20+A22+2*A18+2*A15+A21$	T-S-A25	T-S-A26	T-S-A28	T-A19-A20-A22-A18-A21-A27-A17
T-S-A18	S-M-A15	S-A13-M	$2*A11-3*A4-A13-A8+A9+M$	$3*A4-3*S+2*A13+A14+2*A8+A9-A10+2*A15+2*M$	S-A14-M	S-A8-A9-A10-A11-A15	A18
T-S-A19	S-M-A9	A1	A4+M-A6-A1	A6-A3-A4	A3	A9	A19
T-S-A20	S-M-A10	A6	A4	A5	M-A4-A5-A6	A10	A20
T-S-A21	S-M-A11	A2+A3-A6	A1+A2-A5	M-A1-A2-A4	A4+A5+A6-A2-A3	A11	A21
T-S-A22	S-M-A8	M-A1-A2-A3	A5-A2-2*A4+A6	A1+A2+A3+2*A4-A5-A6	A2	A8	A22
T-S-A17	$A8-4*S+A9+A10+A11+A15+5*M$	A13	$S-2*A11+3*A4+A13+A8-A9-2*M$	$4*S+A11-3*A4-2*A13-A14-2*A8-A10-2*A15-3*M$	A14	A15	A17
$A27+A17+7*S+A19+A20+A22+A18+A21-6*T$	$A24+2*A13+2*A8+5*M+3*A4+A18+2*A15-T-A17+2*A14-4*S$	A24	$8*T-A28-2*A27-2*A14-3*S-A26-A25-2*A24-2*A13-2*A8-5*M-3*A4-A19-A20-A22-2*A18-2*A15-A21$	A25	A26	A28	A27

Details:

It is a single-digit bordered semi-magic square of order 8 embedded with single-digit bordered semi-magic square of order 6. These are semi-magic only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need some conditions. It is as given below

$$M = \frac{2}{3} \times S \quad \text{and} \quad S = \frac{3}{4} \times T, \quad (2)$$

where M, S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.2. First example is of semi-magic square and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the conditions given in (2)

Example 4.3. Let's consider a following *semi-magic* square based on the Result 4.1:

2a	semi	S=3*T/4 and M=2*S/3							170
	35	291	38	-265	37	36	34	64	270
	43	56	58	99	-168	57	98	27	270
	42	61	11	107	-11	13	19	28	270
	41	60	16	14	15	75	20	29	270
	40	59	9	8	83	20	21	30	270
	39	62	84	-9	33	12	18	31	270
	44	-98	22	-19	248	23	24	26	270
	-14	-221	32	335	33	34	36	35	270
	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270	270

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 120$, $S_{Sm_{6 \times 6}} := 200$ and $L_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} := 270$.

Example 4.4. Let's consider a following *magic* square with *even* number magic sum based on the Result 4.2:

2b	mgc	S=3*T/4 and M=2*S/3							220
	20	136	23	-35	22	21	19	14	220
	28	31	33	89	-83	32	63	27	220
	27	36	11	97	-11	13	19	28	220
	26	35	16	14	15	65	20	29	220
	25	34	9	8	73	20	21	30	220
	24	37	74	-9	33	12	18	31	220
	29	-8	22	-34	138	23	24	26	220
	41	-81	32	90	33	34	36	35	220
	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220	220

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic square are $M_{4 \times 4} := 110$, $S_{6 \times 6} := 165$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 220$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the conditions given in (2).

Result 4.3. *Let's consider following semi-magic square of order 8 with reduced entries:*

T-S-A28	$2*T+3*S+A30-A25-A31$	T-S-A25	$A29+2*A28-7*T+2*S+A27+A26+2*A25+A32+A33+A35+2*A31+A34$	T-S-A26	T-S-A27	T-S-A29	T-A32-A33-A35-A31-A34-A28-A30
T-S-A31	$A19+A20+A21+A22+A23-A4-A7-A11-A15$	A4	A7	A11	A15	S-A19-A20-A21-A22-A23	A31
T-S-A32	S-A12-A5-A8-A16-A19	A5	A8	A12	A16	A19	A32
T-S-A33	$A4+A7+A11+A15-A20-A21-A22-A23-A1-A2-A3+A5+A8+A12+A16$	$S-A4-A5-A12+A21+A22+A23-A17-A7-A8-A15-A16-A13-A9-A11+A1+A2+A3$	A9	A13	A17	A20	A33
T-S-A34	A1	$S+A16+A13+A6-A19+A3-A1-A18-A14-2*A21-A22-A23-A20$	$A21+A22+A23+A20-A16-A13-A6+A19-A3$	A14	A18	A21	A34
T-S-A35	A2	A6	$S+A16+A13-A9+A6-A19+A3-A10-A21-A22-A23-A20-A7-A8$	$A5+A14+A10+2*A21+A22+3*A23+2*A20-A4+A8-A15-A16-A13+2*A9-2*A6+2*A19-A11-A2-A3-S$	$S-A19-A20-A21-A22-2*A23+A4+A7+A11+A15-A5-A9-A14$	A22	A35
T-S-A30	A3	$A12+A18+A14+A21+A20+A17+A7+A8+A15+A9-2*A6+A19+A11-A2-2*A3-S$	A10	$2*S+A4-A8+A15+A16-2*A9+2*A6-2*A19+A2+A3-A12-A5-2*A14-A10-2*A21-A22-3*A23-2*A20$	$A19+A20+A21+A22+2*A23-A4-A7-A11+A5+A9+A14-2*A15-A16-A17-A18$	A23	A30
$A28+A30+7*S+A32+A33+A35+A31+A34-6*T$	$A25+A31-T-A30-4*S$	A25	$8*T-A29-2*A28-3*S-A27-A26-2*A25-A32-A33-A35-2*A31-A34$	A26	A27	A29	A28

Details:

It is a single-digit bordered semi-magic square of order 8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. These are semi-magic only at one diagonal. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (1), where S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 6 and 8 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.3. First example is of semi-magic square and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 4.5. *Let's consider a following semi-magic square based on the Result 4.3:*

3a	semi								280
	2	844	5	-566	4	3	1	-93	200
	-1	78	14	17	21	25	5	41	200
	-2	50	15	18	22	26	29	42	200
	-3	-4	65	19	23	27	30	43	200
	-4	11	-11	77	24	28	31	44	200
	-5	12	16	9	100	-9	32	45	200
	0	13	61	20	-30	63	33	40	200
	213	-804	35	606	36	37	39	38	200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic square are $S_{6 \times 6} := 160$ and $L_{Sm_{8 \times 8}} := 200$.

Example 4.6. Let's consider a following magic square with even number magic sum based on the Result 4.3:

3b	mgc	S=3*T/4							200
	12	814	15	-586	14	13	11	-93	200
	9	78	14	17	21	25	-5	41	200
	8	40	15	18	22	26	29	42	200
	7	-4	55	19	23	27	30	43	200
	6	11	-21	77	24	28	31	44	200
	5	12	16	-1	110	-19	32	45	200
	10	13	71	20	-50	63	33	40	200
	143	-764	35	636	36	37	39	38	200
	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200

The **magic** sums of above magic squares are $S_{6 \times 6} := 150$ and $T_{8 \times 8} := 200$. It is a magic square as it satisfies the condition given in (1).

Result 4.4. *Let's consider following semi-magic square of order 8 with reduced entries:*

$T-2*M-A23$	$2*T+3*2*M+A25-A20-A15$	$T-2*M-A20$	$A24+2*A23-7*T+2*2*M+A22+A21+2*A20+A16+A17+A19+2*A15+A18$	$T-2*M-A21$	$T-2*M-A22$	$T-2*M-A24$	$T-A16-A17-A19-A15-A18-A23-A25$
$T-2*M-A15$	A1	M-A1-A2	A2	$4*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-2*A5-2*A4-A6$	$A5+2*A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	A5	A15
$T-2*M-A16$	$A1+A2+2*A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	$3*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-A1-A3$	M-A2-A3	$2*A5+A4+A6+2*A9+A7+2*A8+A10-3*M$	$3*M-2*A9-A7-2*A8-A10-A5-A4$	M-A5-A6	A16
$T-2*M-A17$	$4*M-2*A11-A12-A13-2*A14-2*A1-A2-2*A3$	$2*A1+A2+A3+2*A11+A12+A13+2*A14-3*M$	A3	A4	M-A4-A6	A6	A17
$T-2*M-A18$	A7	M-A7-A9	A9	A11	M-A11-A13	A13	A18
$T-2*M-A19$	M-A7-A8	$A7+A8+A9+A10-M$	M-A9-A10	M-A11-A12	$A11+A12+A13+A14-M$	M-A13-A14	A19
$T-2*M-A25$	A8	M-A8-A10	A10	A12	M-A12-A14	A14	A25
$A23+A25+14*M+A16+A17+A19+A15+A18-6*T$	$A20+A15-T-A25-4*2*M$	A20	$8*T-A24-2*A23-3*2*M-A22-A21-2*A20-A16-A17-A19-2*A15-A18$	A21	A22	A24	A23

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is composed of 4 equal sums **semi-magic squares** of order 3. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (1), where S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 6 and 8 respectively. The magic sum of order 6 is $S = 2 \times M$, where M is the **semi-magic sum** of order 3.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.4. First example is of **semi-magic square** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 4.7. *Let's consider a following examples based on the Result 4.4:*

8x8	semi								130	8x8	mgc								160
	-36	593	-27	20	-30	-33	-39	-298	150		-36	643	-27	-30	-30	-33	-39	-288	160
	-12	10	32	13	-82	115	22	52	150		-12	10	37	13	-62	100	22	52	160
	-15	157	-128	26	118	-71	8	55	150		-15	142	-113	31	103	-56	13	55	160
	-18	-112	151	16	19	11	25	58	150		-18	-92	136	16	19	16	25	58	160
	-21	28	-7	34	40	-31	46	61	150		-21	28	-2	34	40	-26	46	61	160
	-24	-4	75	-16	-28	123	-40	64	150		-24	1	70	-11	-23	118	-35	64	160
	-42	31	-13	37	43	-37	49	82	150		-42	31	-8	37	43	-32	49	82	160
	318	-553	67	20	70	73	79	76	150		328	-603	67	70	70	73	79	76	160
	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150	150		160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic squares of orders 3, 6 and 10 are given by

First Example

$$M_{6 \times 6} := 55(\text{semi} - \text{magic})$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 110$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 150$$

Second Example

$$M_{6 \times 6} := 60(\text{semi} - \text{magic})$$

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 120$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 160$$

Result 4.5. *Let's consider following semi-magic square of order 8 with reduced entries:*

T-3*m-A23	2*T+3*3*m+A1 4-A20-A15	T-3*m-A20	A24+2*A23- 7*T+2*3*m+A22+A21 +2*A20+A16+A17+A19 +2*A15+A18	T-3*m-A21	T-3*m-A22	T-3*m-A24	T-A16-A17- A19-A15-A18- A23-A14
T-3*m-A15	A1-A6+A7- A12+A13	A1	3*m-2*A1-A2-A3- A4+A6-A7+A12-A13	A2	A3	A4	A15
T-3*m-A16	m+A6-A7+A12- A13-A1	m-A1	2*A1+A2+A3+A4- A6+A7-A12+A13-2*m	m-A2	m-A3	m-A4	A16
T-3*m-A17	A5	3*m-A5-A6-A7- A8-A9	A6	A7	A8	A9	A17
T-3*m-A18	m-A5	A5+A6+A7+A8 +A9-2*m	m-A6	m-A7	m-A8	m-A9	A18
T-3*m-A19	A4+A7- A6+A10-A3	A10	3*m-A4-A7+A6- 2*A10+A3-A11-A12-A13	A11	A12	A13	A19
T-3*m-A14	m-A4-A7+A6- A10+A3	m-A10	A4+A7-A6+2*A10- A3+A11+A12+A13-2*m	m-A11	m-A12	m-A13	A14
A23+A14+7*3*m + A16+A17+A19 +A15+A18-6*T	A20+A15-T- A14-4*3*m	A20	8*T-A24-2*A23-3*3*m- A22-A21-2*A20-A16-A17 -A19-2*A15-A18	A21	A22	A24	A23

Details:

It is a **single-digit bordered semi-magic square** of order 8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is composed of 3 equal sums **magic rectangles** of order $m \times 3m$. In order to bring it as a magic square we need a condition given in (1), where S and T are magic sums of magic squares of orders 6 and 8 respectively.

Below are two examples based on the Result 4.5. First example is of **semi-magic square** and the second example as a magic square obtained by applying the condition given in (1).

Example 4.8. *Let's consider a following semi-magic and magic squares of order 8:*

8x8	semi									216	8x8	mgc									144
	-14	516	-11	-266	-12	-13	-15	-65	120		4	582	7	-422	6	5	3	-41	144		
	-6	12	10	44	11	12	13	24	120		12	12	10	50	11	12	13	24	144		
	-7	22	24	-10	23	22	21	25	120		11	24	26	-14	25	24	23	25	144		
	-8	14	22	15	16	17	18	26	120		10	14	28	15	16	17	18	26	144		
	-9	20	12	19	18	17	16	27	120		9	22	8	21	20	19	18	27	144		
	-10	21	19	-1	20	21	22	28	120		8	21	19	5	20	21	22	28	144		
	-5	13	15	35	14	13	12	23	120		13	15	17	31	16	15	14	23	144		
	179	-498	29	284	30	31	33	32	120		77	-546	29	458	30	31	33	32	144		
	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120		144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144	144		

The **magic** and **semi-magic** sums of above magic squares of orders 6 and 10 are given by

First Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 102$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 120$$

Second Example

$$S_{6 \times 6} := 108$$

$$T_{8 \times 8} := 144.$$

The magic rectangles sums is 34×102 and 36×108 .

5 Self-Made Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 8

Below are ten results on **algebraic pandiagonal** magic squares of order 8 for the **reduced entries**. These are of different types, such as, **single-digit bordered**, **double-digit bordered**, **striped**, **block-wise**, **cornered**, etc.

5.1 Self-Made Four Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 4

Result 5.1. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

$A_2 - A_{10} + A_6$	$A_3 + A_5 - A_{11} - A_{13} + A_7 + A_9 - A_1$	$A_4 + A_{13} + A_1 - A_9 + A_8 - A_5 - A_{12}$	$S - A_2 + A_{10} - A_6 - A_3 + A_{11} - A_7 + A_{12} - A_4 - A_8$	A_2	A_3	A_4	$S - A_2 - A_3 - A_4$
A_1	$S - A_2 + A_{10} - A_6 - A_3 - A_5 + A_{11} + A_{13} - A_7 - A_9$	$A_2 - A_{10} + A_6 + A_{12} - A_4 - A_{13} + A_9 - A_8 + A_5$	$A_3 - A_{11} + A_7 - A_{12} + A_4 - A_1 + A_8$	A_5	$S - A_2 - A_3 - A_5$	$A_2 - A_4 + A_5$	$A_3 + A_4 - A_5$
$(1/2) * S + A_{12} - A_4 - A_{13} - A_1 + A_9 - A_8 + A_5$	$A_2 - A_{10} + A_6 + A_3 - A_{11} + A_7 - A_{12} + A_4 + A_8 - (1/2) * S$	$(1/2) * S - A_2 + A_{10} - A_6$	$(1/2) * S + A_1 - A_3 - A_5 + A_{11} + A_{13} - A_7 - A_9$	$S/2 - A_4$	$A_2 + A_3 + A_4 - S/2$	$S/2 - A_2$	$S/2 - A_3$
$(1/2) * S - A_2 + A_{10} - A_6 - A_{12} + A_4 + A_{13} - A_9 + A_8 - A_5$	$(1/2) * S + A_1 - A_3 + A_{11} - A_7 + A_{12} - A_4 - A_8$	$S/2 - A_1$	$A_2 - A_{10} + A_6 + A_3 + A_5 - A_{11} - A_{13} + A_7 + A_9 - (1/2) * S$	$S/2 - A_2 + A_4 - A_5$	$S/2 - A_3 - A_4 + A_5$	$S/2 - A_5$	$A_2 + A_3 + A_5 - S/2$
A_6	A_7	A_8	$S - A_6 - A_7 - A_8$	A_{10}	A_{11}	A_{12}	$S - A_{10} - A_{11} - A_{12}$
A_9	$S - A_6 - A_7 - A_9$	$A_6 - A_8 + A_9$	$A_7 + A_8 - A_9$	A_{13}	$S - A_{10} - A_{11} - A_{13}$	$A_{10} - A_{12} + A_{13}$	$A_{11} + A_{12} - A_{13}$
$S/2 - A_8$	$A_6 + A_7 + A_8 - S/2$	$S/2 - A_6$	$S/2 - A_7$	$S/2 - A_{12}$	$A_{10} + A_{11} + A_{12} - S/2$	$S/2 - A_{10}$	$S/2 - A_{11}$
$S/2 - A_6 + A_8 - A_9$	$S/2 - A_7 - A_8 + A_9$	$S/2 - A_9$	$A_6 + A_7 + A_9 - S/2$	$S/2 - A_{10} + A_{12} - A_{13}$	$S/2 - A_{11} - A_{12} + A_{13}$	$S/2 - A_{13}$	$A_{10} + A_{11} + A_{13} - S/2$

Details:

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 composed of four equal sums *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 4. The letter S represents the magic sums of magic squares of order 4. In this case $T = 2 \times S$ is the magic square of order 8. In order to avoid *fractional* entries the magic sums of order 4 should be multiple of 2. Moreover, the magic squares of orders 4 and 8 are *pandiagonal* See below two examples:

Example 5.1. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96		pan	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68
96	3	6	9	30	15	18	21	-6	96	68	3	6	9	16	15	18	21	-20	68
96	12	27	6	3	24	-9	18	15	96	68	12	13	6	3	24	-23	18	15	68
96	15	-6	21	18	3	30	9	6	96	68	8	1	14	11	-4	37	2	-1	68
96	18	21	12	-3	6	9	0	33	96	68	11	14	5	4	-1	2	-7	40	68
96	27	30	33	-42	39	42	45	-78	96	68	27	30	33	-56	39	42	45	-92	68
96	36	-45	30	27	48	-81	42	39	96	68	36	-59	30	27	48	-95	42	39	68
96	-9	66	-3	-6	-21	102	-15	-18	96	68	-16	73	-10	-13	-28	109	-22	-25	68
	-6	-3	-12	69	-18	-15	-24	105	96		-13	-10	-19	76	-25	-22	-31	112	68
	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96		68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68	68

According to Result 5.1, the magic sums are 96 and 68, where 48 and 34 are the sums of the magic squares of order 4 respectively. Moreover, the magic squares of orders 4 and 8 are **pandiagonal**.

5.2 Self-Made Striped Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 8

Result 5.2. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

$A3+A5-A6$	$A6+A1+A2-2*m-A5$	$2*m$	$2*m-A3-A1-A2$	$2*A3-A4+3*A5-A1-2*A6-A2+2*m$	$2*A1-3*A5+2*A2+A4+2*A6-4*m-A3$	$A5-A1+2*m$	$2*m-A3-A5-A2$
$m-A3-A5+A6$	$3*m+A5-A6-A1-A2$	$(-m)$	$A3+A1-m+A2$	$A4-3*A5+A1+2*A6+A2-m-2*A3$	$A3-2*A1+3*A5-2*A2+5*m-A4-2*A6$	$A1-m-A5$	$A3+A5+A2-m$
$(-A3-A2)$	$A1$	$A6-A5+A2$	$2*m+A3+A5-A1-A6$	$A1-A3-A2-A5$	$A5$	$A4-3*A5+2*A6+A1+2*A2-2*m-A3$	$2*A3-A4+3*A5-2*A1-2*A6-A2+4*m$
$m+A3+A2$	$m-A1$	$A5-A6-A2+m$	$A6+A1-A3-A5-m$	$A3+A5-A1+A2+m$	$m-A5$	$A3+3*A5-A1-A4-2*A2+3*m-2*A6$	$A4-3*A5+2*A1+2*A6+A2-3*m-2*A3$
$A1+A4-2*A3-2*A5$	$2*m-A3-A2-A4$	$2*A3+2*A5-A1+A2$	$A3$	$2*m-A6-A3-A2$	$A6-2*A3-2*A5+A1$	$2*A3+3*A5-2*A1+A2$	$A3-A5+A1$
$2*A3-A4+2*A5-A1+m$	$A3+A2+A4-m$	$m-2*A3-2*A5+A1-A2$	$m-A3$	$A3+A6+A2-m$	$m+2*A3+2*A5-A1-A6$	$m-2*A3-3*A5+2*A1-A2$	$m-A3+A5-A1$
$A1-A3-2*A5$	$A2$	$A3-A4+2*A5-A1-A2+2*m$	$A4$	$2*A1-A3-3*A5$	$A5+A2-A1$	$A6$	$A3+2*A5-A6-A1-A2+2*m$
$A3+2*A5-A1+m$	$m-A2$	$A4-2*A5+A1+A2-m-A3$	$m-A4$	$m+A3+3*A5-2*A1$	$m-A5-A2+A1$	$m-A6$	$A6+A1+A2-m-A3-2*A5$

Details:

It is an *algebraic pandiagonal striped* magic square of order 8 where the magic rectangles of order 2×4 are of equal width and length, i.e., $m \times 2m$. In this case the magic sum of order 8 is $T = 4 \times m$. It includes five magic squares of order 4 also. These are specified below in examples.

Example 5.2. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		pan	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
100	23	-4	50	-19	54	-35	58	-27	100	100	23	-4	50	-19	54	-35	58	-27	100
100	2	29	-25	44	-29	60	-33	52	100	100	2	29	-25	44	-29	60	-33	52	100
100	-48	21	25	52	-56	29	-6	83	100	100	-48	21	25	52	-56	29	-6	83	100
100	73	4	0	-27	81	-4	31	-58	100	100	73	4	0	-27	81	-4	31	-58	100
100	-60	-25	110	25	-29	-56	118	17	100	100	-60	-25	110	25	-29	-56	118	17	100
100	85	50	-85	0	54	81	-93	8	100	100	85	50	-85	0	54	81	-93	8	100
100	-62	23	62	27	-70	31	31	58	100	100	-62	23	62	27	-70	31	31	58	100
	87	2	-37	-2	95	-6	-6	-33	100		87	2	-37	-2	95	-6	-6	-33	100
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

According to Result 5.2, the magic sums are 100 and 96 with sums of *magic rectangles* $100 = 4 \times 25$ and $100 = 4 \times 24$ respectively, where 25 and 24 are the sums of *magic rectangles* of order 2×4 . Moreover each magic square of order 8 is with five magic squares of order 4. See below

	pan	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		pan	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96
100	23	-4	50	-19	54	-35	58	-27	100	96	23	-2	48	-21	52	-31	56	-29	96
100	2	29	-25	44	-29	60	-33	52	100	96	1	26	-24	45	-28	55	-32	53	96
100	-48	21	25	52	-56	29	-6	83	100	96	-48	21	25	50	-56	29	-4	79	96
100	73	4	0	-27	81	-4	31	-58	100	96	72	3	-1	-26	80	-5	28	-55	96
100	-60	-25	110	25	-29	-56	118	17	100	96	-60	-27	110	25	-31	-56	118	17	96
100	85	50	-85	0	54	81	-93	8	100	96	84	51	-86	-1	55	80	-94	7	96
100	-62	23	62	27	-70	31	31	58	100	96	-62	23	60	27	-70	31	31	56	96
	87	2	-37	-2	95	-6	-6	-33	100		86	1	-36	-3	94	-7	-7	-32	96
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96

More precisely, these are

5.3 Self-Made Double-Digit Bordered Pandiagonal Magic Square of Order 8

Result 5.3. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

$A_6+A_8+(1/2)*A_1+(1/2)*A_2-(1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*A_1+(3/2)*A_2+A_3-A_4+A_{13}-(1/2)*M$	$A_{11}+A_{10}-A_7$	A_7	$M-A_8-A_{11}-A_{10}$	A_8	$A_6-A_3+A_4+A_8-A_{13}-A_2+A_{12}$	$2*M-2*A_6-2*A_8-A_1-A_2-A_{12}$
$A_4-A_{13}-A_3$	$M-A_6-A_8-A_2$	$A_7-A_{11}-A_{10}+(1/2)*M$	$(2*M-M)/2-A_7$	$A_8+A_{11}+A_{10}-(1/2)*M$	$(2*M-M)/2-A_8$	$A_2+A_1+A_3-A_4-A_{12}$	$A_6+A_8+A_{13}-A_1+A_{12}$
$2*M-2*A_6-A_4-2*A_8-A_{11}-A_{12}$	$2*A_6+A_4+2*A_8+A_{11}+A_{12}-(3/2)*M$	A_1	$(3/2)*M-(1/2)*A_2-(3/2)*A_1-A_5$	$A_5-A_3-(1/2)*M+(1/2)*A_2+(1/2)*A_1$	A_3	$(3/2)*M-A_6-A_8-A_{11}-A_9-A_{10}$	$A_6+A_8+A_{11}+A_9+A_{10}-M$
$A_4-A_{10}+A_{12}$	$A_{10}-A_{12}+(1/2)*M-A_4$	A_5	$(1/2)*M-(1/2)*A_2-(1/2)*A_1$	A_4	$(1/2)*M+(1/2)*A_2+(1/2)*A_1-A_4-A_5$	$(1/2)*M-A_6-A_8+A_9$	$A_6+A_8-A_9$
$A_6-M+2*A_8+A_{11}+A_{10}$	$(3/2)*M-A_6-2*A_8-A_{11}-A_{10}$	$A_2+A_3-A_5$	$A_1+A_2-A_4$	$(1/2)*M-(1/2)*A_2-(1/2)*A_1$	$(1/2)*M-(3/2)*A_2-(1/2)*A_1+A_4+A_5-A_3$	$2*A_6+A_4+2*A_8+A_7+A_{12}-(3/2)*M$	$2*M-2*A_6-A_4-2*A_8-A_7-A_{12}$
A_6	$(2*M-M)/2-A_6$	$M-A_1-A_2-A_3$	$A_4-M+A_1+A_5$	$A_3+M-A_4-A_5$	A_2	$(1/2)*M-A_4-A_7+A_{11}+A_{10}-A_{12}$	$A_4+A_7-A_{11}-A_{10}+A_{12}$
$(3/2)*M-A_6+A_3-A_4-A_8+A_{13}-(1/2)*A_1-(1/2)*A_2-A_{12}$	$2*A_6-A_3+A_4+2*A_8+A_{12}-M$	$A_9+A_{10}+A_{11}-(1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A_9$	$(1/2)*M-A_{10}$	$(1/2)*M-A_{11}$	$M-A_6-A_8-A_1$	$(3/2)*A_1+(1/2)*A_2-(1/2)*M-A_{13}$
A_{12}	$(3/2)*M-A_6-A_8-A_{13}-(1/2)*A_1-(1/2)*A_2-A_{12}$	$M-A_9-A_{10}-A_{11}$	A_9	A_{10}	A_{11}	A_{13}	$A_6+A_8+(1/2)*A_1+(1/2)*A_2-(1/2)*M$

Details:

It is an *algebraic double-digits bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 where the magic rectangles of order 2×4 are of equal width and length. The internal magic square of order 4 is also a *pandiagonal*. The letter M represents the magic sums of magic squares of order 4. In this case, $T = 2 \times M$, where T is the magic sums of order 8. Both the magic squares of orders 4 and 8 are *pandiagonal*. There is interesting observation that the first two entries i.e., A1 and A2 should be an even number, otherwise we shall get decimal entries. See below two examples.

Example 5.3. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		pan	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132
100	48	47	51	30	-64	33	46	-91	100	132	40	39	51	30	-48	33	46	-59	132
100	-45	-24	-26	-5	89	-8	-22	141	100	132	-45	-8	-18	3	81	0	-22	141	132
100	-128	153	12	26	-6	18	-102	127	100	132	-96	129	12	50	-14	18	-78	111	132
100	27	-2	24	12	21	-7	1	24	100	132	27	6	24	20	21	1	9	24	132
100	124	-99	8	5	12	25	141	-116	100	132	108	-75	8	5	20	33	117	-84	132
100	27	-2	6	7	23	14	10	15	100	132	27	6	22	-9	39	14	18	15	132
100	2	118	92	-11	-14	-17	-22	-48	100	132	26	102	84	-3	-6	-9	-6	-56	132
	45	-91	-67	36	39	42	48	48	100		45	-67	-51	36	39	42	48	40	132
	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100		132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132	132

According to Result 5.3 both the magic square of orders 4 and 8 are **pandiagonal**. The respective magic sums are with magic sums 100 and 132, where 50 and 66 are the magic sums of magic squares of order 4. The magic rectangles sums are 25×50 and 33×66 respectively.

5.4 Self-Made Cornered Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 8

Result 5.4. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

$A_{18}+A_4-A_6+A_{17}+A_8+A_{10}+A_{15}+A_{16}-A_{12}-(2/3)*S$	A1	A2	$A_6-A_{17}-A_8-A_{10}-A_{15}-A_{16}+A_{12}-A_1-A_2+(5/3)*S-A_{18}-A_3-2*A_4$	A3	A4	$(1/3)*S-A_{14}$	A14
A5	A6	A7	$2*A_{18}+A_4+A_{17}+A_{15}+A_{16}-A_9+A_{12}+A_{13}-S$	$(3/2)*S-2*A_{18}+A_3-A_{17}-A_5-2*A_{15}-A_{16}+A_9-A_7-A_6-A_{12}$	$A_{15}-A_{13}+(1/2)*S-A_3-A_4$	$(1/3)*S-A_{15}$	A15
$A_{12}-A_1-A_2+A_{13}+(4/3)*S-A_4-A_{17}-A_8-A_{10}-A_5-A_{15}-A_{16}$	$A_3-A_6+A_{11}-A_7+(1/6)*S$	$S-A_{18}-A_3-A_{12}-A_{11}-A_{13}$	A8	$A_{10}+A_5+A_{15}+A_9-A_{12}+A_1-A_{13}-(1/3)*S$	$A_{18}+A_4+A_6+A_{17}+A_{16}-A_9+A_{12}+A_7+A_2+A_{13}-(7/6)*S$	$(1/3)*S-A_{16}$	A16
$A_1+A_2+A_4+A_8+A_{10}-A_{12}-A_{11}-A_{13}-A_{18}$	A9	A10	$A_{18}+A_3-A_8-A_{10}+A_{12}+A_{11}+A_{13}-(1/3)*S$	$2*S/3-A_3-A_9-A_1$	$2*S/3-A_4-A_2-A_{10}$	$(1/3)*S-A_{17}$	A17
A11	$2*A_{18}-A_3+A_{17}+A_5+2*A_{15}+A_6-A_9+A_7-(5/6)*S$	$A_6-A_{10}-A_{15}-A_9+A_{12}+A_{13}+(1/6)*S$	$A_9-A_{12}-A_{11}-A_{13}+(5/3)*S-2*A_{18}-A_4-A_{17}-A_5-A_{15}-A_{16}$	A12	$A_3+A_4-A_7+A_9-A_6+A_{10}-A_{12}$	$(1/3)*S-A_{18}$	A18
$S/3-A_8-A_4-A_{10}+A_6+A_{12}$	$(5/3)*S-2*A_{18}-A_{17}-A_5-2*A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{11}-A_1$	$A_{18}+A_3-A_6+A_{15}+A_9+A_{11}-A_7-(1/6)*S-A_2$	$2*A_4-A_6+A_{17}+A_8+2*A_{10}+A_5+A_{15}+A_{16}-2*A_{12}+A_1+A_2-A_{13}-S$	$2*A_{18}-A_3+A_6+A_{17}-A_{10}+A_{15}+A_{16}-A_9+A_{12}+A_7+A_{13}-(5/6)*S$	$S-A_{18}-A_4-A_{17}-A_{15}-A_{16}$	$A_{14}+A_{15}+A_{16}+A_{17}+A_{18}-(2/3)*S$	$S-A_{14}-A_{15}-A_{16}-A_{17}-A_{18}$
$A_{18}+A_4-A_6+A_{17}+A_8+A_{10}+A_{15}+A_{16}-A_{12}+A_{14}-(5/6)*S$	$A_{18}+A_4-A_6+A_{17}+A_8+A_{10}+A_5+2*A_{15}+A_{16}-A_{12}+A_1-(7/6)*S$	$A_6-A_{17}-A_8-A_{10}-A_{15}+A_{12}+A_{13}+(1/2)*S-A_4$	$2*S-2*A_4+A_6-A_8-A_{10}-2*A_{16}+A_{12}-2*A_{18}-A_{17}-A_5-2*A_{15}-A_1$	$(1/3)*S-A_{13}$	$A_4-A_{14}+(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$
$A_6-A_{17}-A_8-A_{10}-A_{15}-A_{16}+A_{12}-A_{14}+(7/6)*S-A_{18}-A_4$	$A_6-A_{17}-A_8-A_{10}-A_5-2*A_{15}-A_{16}+A_{12}-A_1+(3/2)*S-A_{18}-A_4$	$A_4-A_6+A_{17}+A_8+A_{10}+A_{15}-A_{12}-A_{13}-(1/6)*S$	$2*A_4-A_6+A_8+A_{10}+2*A_{16}-A_{12}+2*A_{18}+A_{17}+A_5+2*A_{15}-(5/3)*S+A_1$	A13	$(1/6)*S+A_{14}-A_4$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$

Details:

It is an *algebraic cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8, where the *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 is at the upper-left corner. The magic rectangles of order 2×6 are of equal length and width. The letters T and S represents the magic sums of orders 6 and 8, where $T = \frac{4}{3} \times S$. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sum of order 6 must be multiple of 6. Here both the magic squares of orders 6 and 8 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.4. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96		pan	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80
96	202	11	14	-192	17	20	-26	50	96	80	210	11	14	-212	17	20	-30	50	80
96	23	26	29	296	-307	5	-29	53	96	80	23	26	29	308	-325	-1	-33	53	80
96	-119	15	-139	32	45	238	-32	56	96	80	-135	13	-151	32	49	252	-36	56	80
96	-79	35	38	117	-15	-24	-35	59	96	80	-79	35	38	121	-23	-32	-39	59	80
96	41	285	3	-312	44	11	-38	62	96	80	41	295	1	-332	44	11	-42	62	80
96	4	-300	127	131	288	-178	232	-208	96	80	0	-320	129	143	298	-190	240	-220	80
96	240	253	-49	-331	-23	-18	12	12	96	80	250	267	-55	-355	-27	-20	10	10	80
	-216	-229	73	355	47	42	12	12	96		-230	-247	75	375	47	40	10	10	80
	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96		80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80

According to Result 5.4 both the magic square of orders 6 and 8 are **pandiagonal**. The respective magic sums are 72 and 96, and 60 and 90 for the first and second examples. The magic rectangles sums are 24×72 and 20×60 respectively.

Result 5.5. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

A1	$(1/2)*M+(1/3)*S-A1-A3$	$A3+3*M-2*S+A1-A2$	$(5/3)*S-A1-(5/2)*M+A2$	S-M-A5	A5	$A4+(5/6)*S-A10-A7-A5-A9$	$A5+A9-(1/2)*S-A4+A10+A7$
A3	$(1/3)*S-(1/2)*M$	A2	$(3/2)*M-(1/3)*S-A2-A3$	$2*M+A4-(7/6)*S$	$(13/6)*S-A4-3*M$	A7	$(1/3)*S-A7$
$(1/2)*M-A1+A2-A3$	$A1+3*M-(5/3)*S-A2$	$(4/3)*S-(3/2)*M-A1$	$(1/3)*S+A1+A3-M$	$A5-A6-M+(1/2)*S-A4+A2+A10$	$A6+(1/2)*S+A4-A2-A10-A5$	A8	$(1/3)*S-A8$
$(1/2)*M-A2$	$A2-2*M+S+A3$	$(2/3)*S-A3-(1/2)*M$	$3*M-(5/3)*S$	$A6-2*M+(5/3)*S-A2-A10$	$M+A2+A10-A6-(2/3)*S$	$A5-A8+(1/6)*S-A4$	$A8+(1/6)*S+A4-A5$
$(5/6)*S-(3/2)*M+A1+A5$	S-M-A4	$M-(2/3)*S-A2+A9+A7$	$A4+(5/6)*S+A2-A7-(1/2)*M-A5-A1-A9$	$(S-M)/2$	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	A9	$(1/3)*S-A9$
$(1/2)*M+(1/6)*S-A1-A5$	A4	$(5/3)*S-2*M+A2-A9-A7$	$A5+A1-(1/2)*M+A9+(1/6)*S-A4-A2+A7$	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(S-M)/2$	A10	$(1/3)*S-A10$
A6	$A5-A6+(9/2)*M+A9-(19/6)*S-A4+A1+A10$	$(9/2)*M-A1-(5/2)*S-A8$	$A8-M+(2/3)*S+A4-A5$	$(8/3)*S-(7/2)*M-A9$	$(10/3)*S-(9/2)*M-A10$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$
$(1/3)*S-A6$	$A6-(9/2)*M-A9+(7/2)*S+A4-A1-A10-A5$	$(17/6)*S+A8-(9/2)*M+A1$	$M+A5-A4-A8-(1/3)*S$	$(7/2)*M-(7/3)*S+A9$	$(9/2)*M-3*S+A10$	$(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$

Details:

It is an *algebraic cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8, where the magic square of order 4 is at the upper-left corner. The magic square of order 6 is also a *cornered* magic square. The magic rectangles of orders 2×4 and 2×6 are of equal length and width. The letters M, S and T represents the magic sums of orders 4, 6 and 8, where $T = \frac{4}{3} \times S$ and $S = \frac{3}{2} \times M$. In order to avoid decimal entries, the magic sum of order 4 must be multiple of 6. See below two examples:

Example 5.5. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96		pan	104	104	104	104	104	104	104	104
96	11	21	-6	16	15	15	3	21	96	104	11	26	0	11	15	15	8	18	104
96	13	3	12	14	14	16	17	7	96	104	13	2	12	21	19	11	17	9	104
96	9	5	22	6	11	19	18	6	96	104	12	13	21	2	8	22	18	8	104
96	9	13	14	6	20	10	-5	29	96	104	12	7	15	14	18	12	-4	30	104
96	23	16	18	3	15	-3	19	5	96	104	19	16	20	5	15	3	19	7	104
96	7	14	12	27	-3	15	20	4	96	104	11	14	10	25	3	15	20	6	104
96	16	-4	-20	23	26	31	12	12	96	104	16	4	-8	21	21	24	13	13	104
	8	28	44	1	-2	-7	12	12	96		10	22	34	5	5	2	13	13	104
	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96		104	104	104	104	104	104	104	104	104

The respective magic sums of orders 4, 6 and 8 are 42, 72 and 96, and 48, 78 and 104 for the first and second examples. The magic rectangles sums are 30×60 and 24×72 for the first example and 30×60 and 26×78 for the second example.

Result 5.6. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

$2*M/3-A6$	$A6+A7-M/3$	$2*M/3-A7$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A2+A3-M/3$	$2*M/3-A3$	$(8/3)*M-2*M-A15$	$A15$
$A6+A8-M/3$	$M+A1-A6-A7-A8$	$M/3+A7-A1$	$A2-M+A6+A1+A3$	$(7/3)*M-2*A3-A2-A6-A1-A5$	$A3+A5-M/3$	$(2/3)*M+A7+A8-A1-A3+A19-A5-A2$	$A1+A3-A19+A5+A2-A7-A8$
$2*M/3-A8$	$M/3+A8-A1$	$A1$	$(4/3)*M-A6-A1-A3$	$A6+A1+A3+A5-M$	$2*M/3-A5$	$A5+A18+A2-A7-A8$	$(2/3)*M+A7+A8-A5-A18-A2$
$A2$	$M-A2-A3$	$A3$	$A6$	$M-A6-A7$	$A7$	$(2/3)*M-A18$	$A18$
$(5/3)*M-A2-A6-A1-A3$	$A2+2*A3-(5/3)*M+A6+A1+A5$	$M-A3-A5$	$M-A6-A8$	$A6+A7+A8-A1-M/3$	$M/3-A7+A1$	$(2/3)*M-A19$	$A19$
$A6+A1+A3-(2/3)*M$	$(5/3)*M-A6-A1-A3-A5$	$A5$	$A8$	$M/3-A8+A1$	$2*M/3-A1$	$A15+A1+A3-(2/3)*M$	$(4/3)*M-A15-A1-A3$
$(1/3)*M+A15-A6$	$A6+A1+A3-A19+A5+A2-M$	$(2/3)*M-A5+A1-A18+A6-A2$	$(4/3)*M-A7-A6-A8+A18-A1$	$A19+A8+A7-(1/3)*M-A1$	$M-A3-A15$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$
$A6-A15+(1/3)*M$	$(5/3)*M-A1-A3+A19-A5-A2-A6$	$A5-A1+A18-A6+A2$	$A7+A6+A8-A18+A1-(2/3)*M$	$A1+M-A19-A8-A7$	$A3+A15-(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$	$(1/3)*M$

Details:

It is an *algebraic cornered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8, where the *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 is at the upper-left corner. It is composed of four equal sums *semi-magic* squares of order 3. The *magic rectangles* of order 2×6 are of equal length and width. The letters M, S and T represents the magic sums of orders 3, 6 and 8, where $T = \frac{8}{3} \times M$ and $S = 2 \times M$. In order to avoid decimal entries, the *semi-magic* sum of order 3 must be multiple of 3. Both the magic squares of orders 6 and 8 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.6. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128		pan	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136
128	5	42	1	17	18	13	-7	39	128	136	7	41	3	19	17	15	-5	39	136
128	46	-34	36	24	-2	26	77	-45	128	136	45	-31	37	21	5	25	79	-45	136
128	-3	40	11	7	32	9	15	17	128	136	-1	41	11	11	29	11	15	19	136
128	15	14	19	27	-10	31	-11	43	128	136	15	17	19	27	-7	31	-9	43	136
128	8	34	6	-14	66	-4	-15	47	128	136	13	29	9	-11	65	-3	-13	47	136
128	25	0	23	35	-8	21	37	-5	128	136	23	5	23	35	-7	23	35	-1	136
128	28	0	-11	3	86	-10	16	16	128	136	29	-3	-9	7	85	-7	17	17	136
	4	32	43	29	-54	42	16	16	128		5	37	43	27	-51	41	17	17	136
	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128		136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136	136

The respective magic sums of orders 3, 6 and 8 are 48, 96 and 128, and 51, 102 and 136 for the first and second examples. The magic rectangles sums are 30×60 and 24×72 for the first example and 32×96 and 34×102 for the second example.

Result 5.7. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

$(1/4)*M$	$2*A1-2*A6-2*A5+2*A3$	$(1/4)*M-A1+A6+A5-A3$	$A3+A1-(1/4)*M$	$M-2*A1+A6+A5-2*A3$	$(1/4)*M$	$A7$	$(1/2)*M-A7$
$(3/4)*M+2*A6+2*A5-2*A3-3*A1$	$A1$	$A2$	$M-A2-A6-A5$	$A6+A5-A1$	$3*A1-2*A6-2*A5+2*A3-(1/4)*M$	$(5/4)*M-3*A1+2*A6+2*A5-2*A3-A4-A8$	$3*A1-2*A6-2*A5-(3/4)*M+2*A3+A4+A8$
$3*A1+3*A3+A4-2*A6-2*A5-(3/4)*M$	$(7/4)*M-3*A1-A2+A6+A5-2*A3-A4$	$2*A1-A6-A5+2*A3+A4-(3/4)*M$	$(3/4)*M+2*A6+2*A5-2*A3-A4-2*A1$	$3*A1+A2-2*A6-2*A5+2*A3+A4-(3/4)*M$	$(5/4)*M+2*A6+2*A5-3*A1-3*A3-A4$	$2*A1-A6-2*A5+2*A3+A4-(1/2)*M$	$M-2*A1+A6+2*A5-2*A3-A4$
$(1/2)*M-A3$	$A2+A6+A5-(1/2)*M$	$(1/2)*M+A1-A6-A5$	$M/2-A1$	$M/2-A2$	$A3$	$(1/4)*M+A1-A6$	$(1/4)*M-A1+A6$
$(1/2)*M-A4$	$2*A1-2*A6-2*A5+2*A3+A4-(1/4)*M$	$(5/4)*M+2*A6+2*A5-2*A3-A4-A2-3*A1$	$3*A1+A2-A6-A5+2*A3+A4-(5/4)*M$	$(5/4)*M+A6+A5-2*A3-A4-2*A1$	$A4$	$A8$	$(1/2)*M-A8$
$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-2*A1+2*A6+2*A5-2*A3$	$(1/4)*M+A1-A6-A5+A3$	$(3/4)*M-A3-A1$	$2*A1-A6-A5+2*A3-(1/2)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A7$	$A7$
$(1/2)*M-A7$	$2*A3+A4+2*A1+A8-2*A6-2*A5-(1/2)*M$	$A5$	$A6$	$(3/2)*M+A6+A5-2*A3-A4-2*A1-A8$	$A7$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$
$A7$	$M+2*A6+2*A5-2*A3-A4-2*A1-A8$	$(1/2)*M-A5$	$(1/2)*M-A6$	$2*A1-A6-A5+2*A3+A4+A8-M$	$(1/2)*M-A7$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/4)*M$

Details:

It is an *algebraic cornered pandiagonal* magic square of orders 8 and having *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 as the upper-left corner. It contains *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 in the middle. The letters M, S and T represents the magic sums of orders 4, 6 and 8 with $T = 2 \times M$ and $S = \frac{3}{2} \times M$. This means that the magic sum of order 8 depends on the choice of magic square of order 4, i.e., $T = 2 \times M$. To avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. In this case, all the three magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.7. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96			pan	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128
96	12	-70	47	20	51	12	41	-17	96		128	16	-70	51	16	67	16	41	-9	128
96	95	11	16	-35	56	-71	47	-23	96		128	107	11	16	-19	56	-75	67	-35	128
96	-48	34	-13	80	-53	72	-32	56	96		128	-60	62	-25	92	-65	92	-40	72	128
96	3	59	-32	13	8	21	-13	37	96		128	11	51	-24	21	16	21	-9	41	128
96	-2	-56	77	-10	37	26	46	-22	96		128	6	-60	97	-30	57	26	46	-14	128
96	12	94	-23	4	-27	12	-17	41	96		128	16	102	-19	16	-35	16	-9	41	128
96	-17	-22	31	36	3	41	12	12	96		128	-9	-30	31	36	27	41	16	16	128
	41	46	-7	-12	21	-17	12	12	96			41	62	1	-4	5	-9	16	16	128
	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96	96			128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128

The magic sums of first example of order 4, 6 and 8 are 48, 72 and 96 respectively. The magic sums of the second example of orders 4, 6, and 8 are 64, 96 and 128 respectively.

Result 5.8. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

$(12/5)^*m-3*A1-A3$	A1	$(3/5)^*m$	A1	$A3+A1-A2$	A2	$m-A5-A2+A3$	$A5+A2-A3$
$3*A1-(7/5)^*m+A3$	$m-A1$	$(2/5)^*m$	$m-A1$	$m+A2-A3-A1$	$m-A2$	$A2-A4-A3+m$	$A4+A3-A2$
$(9/10)^*m-A1$	$(3/2)^*m-A3-A1$	$A3+A1+A1-(9/10)^*m$	$(3/2)^*m-A3-A1$	$2*A3-A2+3*A1-(3/2)^*m$	$(3/2)^*m-A3-2*A1+A2$	$A3+A1-(2/5)^*m$	$(7/5)^*m-A3-A1$
$(1/10)^*m+A1$	$A3+A1-(1/2)^*m$	$(19/10)^*m-A3-2*A1$	$A3+A1-(1/2)^*m$	$(5/2)^*m-2*A3-3*A1+A2$	$A3+2*A1-A2-(1/2)^*m$	$(7/5)^*m-A3-A1$	$A3+A1-(2/5)^*m$
$(12/5)^*m+A2-2*A3-3*A1$	$A3+A1-A2$	$(3/5)^*m-A3+A2$	$A3+A1-A2$	A1	A3	A4	$m-A4$
$2*A3+3*A1-A2-(7/5)^*m$	$m+A2-A3-A1$	$A3+(2/5)^*m-A2$	$m-A3-A1+A2$	$m-A1$	$m-A3$	A5	$m-A5$
$A5+(19/10)^*m-2*A3-3*A1+A2$	$A4+A3+A1-(1/2)^*m-A2$	A1	$(3/5)^*m-4*A1+4*A1$	$A1+(1/2)^*m-A4$	$(1/2)^*m+A3-A5$	$(1/2)^*m$	$(1/2)^*m$
$2*A3+3*A1-A2-A5-(9/10)^*m$	$(3/2)^*m+A2-A4-A3-A1$	$m-A1$	$(2/5)^*m$	$(1/2)^*m-A1+A4$	$A5+(1/2)^*m-A3$	$(1/2)^*m$	$(1/2)^*m$

Details:

It is an *algebraic cornered pandiagonal* magic square of orders 8 and having *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 as the upper-left corner. It is composed of three equal sums *magic rectangles* of order $m \times 3m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangle. The letters S and T represents the magic sums of orders 6 and 8. In this case, both the magic squares of orders 6 and are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.8. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120			pan	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80
120	26	10	18	10	13	13	11	19	120		80	2	10	12	10	13	13	1	19	80
120	4	20	12	20	17	17	8	22	120		80	18	10	8	10	7	7	-2	22	80
120	17	19	9	19	4	22	14	16	120		80	8	4	18	4	19	7	18	2	80
120	13	11	21	11	26	8	16	14	120		80	12	16	2	16	1	13	2	18	80
120	23	13	15	13	10	16	19	11	120		80	-1	13	9	13	10	16	19	1	80
120	7	17	15	17	20	14	22	8	120		80	21	7	11	7	10	4	22	-2	80
120	30	17	10	18	6	9	15	15	120		80	11	22	10	12	1	4	10	10	80
	0	13	20	12	24	21	15	15	120			9	-2	10	8	19	16	10	10	80
	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120			80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80	80

The magic sums of magic squares of orders 6 and 8 for the first example are 90 and 120, and for the second example are 60 and 80 respectively.

5.5 Self-Made Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order 8 Derived From Semi-Magic Squares

Result 5.9. *Let's consider following pandiagonal square of order 8 with reduced entries:*

$(1/6)*S$	$A2+A5+5*A16+A11+4*A14+A12+(5/6)*S$	$A2+A5+6*A16+A11+A13+5*A14+A15+3*A12-(11/2)*S$	$(-(7/6)*S-A2-A5-4*A16-3*A14)$	$6*S-A2-A5-7*A16+A4-A11-6*A14-A15-3*A12-A13$	$(1/3)*S-A11$	$(1/2)*S-A4-A12$	$(1/6)*S$
$(1/3)*S-A12$	$(-(2/3)*S-A2-A5-5*A16-A11-4*A14)$	A1	A2	A3	$5*A16-A3-A4+A11+4*A14+(5/3)*S-A1+A5$	A4	A12
$(1/3)*S-A13$	$(20/3)*S-A1-3*A12-A16-A14-A15$	A5	$A5+A9+8*A16+A7-A3-A4+A11+6*A14+2*A15+3*A12+2*A13-(37/6)*S$	$A10-A7+A4-A11-A14-A15-A13+S-2*A16$	$2*S/3-A9-A5-A10$	$A1-A5-5*A16+A3-4*A14-A13-(7/6)*S$	A13
$(1/3)*S-A14$	$5*A16+5*A14+A15+3*A12-(14/3)*S$	$A8-A5-A9-3*A16-A7-2*A14-2*A15-3*A12-2*A13+8*S-A1$	$A1-A8-A5-4*A16-A10+A3+A4-4*A14-(4/3)*S$	A6	$A7-A4-4*A14-3*A12+5*S-A2-5*A16-A6$	$A2+2*A5+A9+A10-A3+5*A14+A15+3*A12+2*A13+7*A16-6*S$	A14
$(1/3)*S-A15$	$A1-A8-3*A16-3*A14+A15+A13-2*S$	A7	$A10-A6-A4-A11-3*A14+A15+A13-(4/3)*S-A2-4*A16$	$A2-A1+A8+A5+8*A16-A3+A11+7*A14-A15-A13+(10/3)*S$	$A3+A4-A7-S-A5-5*A16-A11-4*A14$	$4*A16-A10+A6+A11+3*A14-A15-A13+2*S$	A15
$(1/3)*S-A16$	A8	A9	$A2+A5+4*A16+A6-A7+A4+3*A14-A15+(3/2)*S$	$A1-A8+3*A16-A10+A7-A4+A11+2*A14+2*A15+3*A12+A13-7*S$	A10	$(13/2)*S-A2-A1-A5-A9-7*A16-A6-A11-5*A14-A15-3*A12-A13$	A16
$A16+A14+A15+A12+A13-(2/3)*S$	$A2+A5+4*A16+A11+3*A14-A15-A13+(5/3)*S$	$2*A14+2*A15+3*A12+2*A13-7*S-A8+3*A16$	$A8-A5-A9-4*A16-2*A14-2*A15-3*A12-3*A13+(25/3)*S-A2-A1$	$A13+(11/3)*S-A2-A5-9*A16-A6-A11-8*A14-3*A12$	$A2+A1+A5+A9+5*A16+A6+A4+4*A14+3*A12-(16/3)*S$	$A16-A4+A14+A15+A13-(1/3)*S$	$S-A16-A14-A15-A12-A13$
$(1/6)*S$	$(-A2-(1/2)*S-A5-5*A16-A11-4*A14-A12)$	$(35/6)*S-A5-6*A16-A11-A13-5*A14-A15-3*A12-A2$	$A2+A5+3*A14+4*A16+(3/2)*S$	$A2+A5+7*A16-A4+A11+6*A14+A15+3*A12+A13-(17/3)*S$	A11	$A4+A12-(1/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S$

Details:

It is an algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal magic square of order 8 embedded with a pandiagonal magic square of order 6. The letters S and T represents the magic sums of orders 6 and 8, where $T = \frac{4}{3} \times S$. Both the magic squares of orders 6 and 8 are pandiagonal. In order de avoid decimal entries, we must have magic sum of order 6 as multiple of 6. See below two examples:

Example 5.9. *Let's consider following two examples representing pandiagonal magic squares of order 8.*

	pan	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64		pan	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72
64	8	489	403	-363	-440	-15	-26	8	64	72	9	494	370	-370	-404	-13	-23	9	72
64	-17	-448	11	13	15	440	17	33	64	72	-15	-452	11	13	15	450	17	33	72
64	-19	93	19	569	-153	-43	-437	35	64	72	-17	133	19	532	-147	-39	-444	35	72
64	-21	304	-115	-406	21	-240	484	37	64	72	-19	276	-67	-414	21	-210	448	37	72
64	-23	-270	23	-318	735	-442	320	39	64	72	-21	-282	23	-326	755	-448	332	39	72
64	-25	25	27	355	67	29	-455	41	64	72	-23	25	27	364	25	29	-416	41	72
64	153	344	83	-165	-637	304	119	-137	64	72	149	354	41	-115	-615	272	117	-131	72
	8	-473	-387	379	456	31	42	8	64		9	-476	-352	388	422	31	41	9	72
	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64		72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72

The magic sums order 6 and 8 of the first example are 48 and 64, and the second example are 54 and 72 respectively. In both the examples, the magic sums 6 and 8 are **pandiagonal**.

Result 5.10. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with *reduced entries*:

$M-A3-A5$	$A7+A3+A5-M+A10-A4+A8$	$(1/3)*M-A10+A4$	$A4+A9-A8-A10+A1$	$(2/3)*M-A9+A8+A10-A4-A1$	$(1/3)*M-A1+A10$	$(5/3)*M+A1-A6-A2-A7-A8-A10$	$A6+A2-(1/3)*M$
$(2/3)*M-A7$	$A1$	$M/3-A1+A2$	$2*M/3-A2$	$A3$	$M/3-A3+A4$	$2*M/3-A4$	$A7$
$(2/3)*M-A8$	$M-A1-A2$	$M/3$	$A2+A1-M/3$	$M-A3-A4$	$M/3$	$A4+A3-M/3$	$A8$
$(2/3)*M-A9$	$A2$	$M/3+A1-A2$	$2*M/3-A1$	$A4$	$M/3+A3-A4$	$2*M/3-A3$	$A9$
$A9$	$A5$	$(1/3)*M-A5+A8+A10-A1$	$(2/3)*M-A8-A10+A1$	$A10-A4+A8$	$(1/3)*M-A10+A4-A8+A6$	$2*M/3-A6$	$(2/3)*M-A9$
$(2/3)*M-A10$	$M-A5-A8-A10+A1$	$M/3$	$A8+A10-A1+A5-(1/3)*M$	$M-A10+A4-A8-A6$	$M/3$	$A6-(1/3)*M+A10-A4+A8$	$A10$
$A6+A2+A7+A8+A10-2*M+A5+A3$	$A8+A10-A1$	$(1/3)*M+A5-A8-A10+A1$	$2*M/3-A5$	$A6$	$(1/3)*M+A10-A4+A8-A6$	$(2/3)*M-A10+A4-A8$	$(8/3)*M-A6-A2-A7-A8-A10-A5-A3$
$M-A6-A2$	$(5/3)*M-A7-A3-A5+A4-A8-A10$	$(1/3)*M-A4+A10$	$(2/3)*M-A9+A8+A10-A4-A1$	$A4+A9-A8-A10+A1$	$(1/3)*M+A1-A10$	$A6+A2+A7+A8+A10-M-A1$	$A3+A5-(1/3)*M$

Details:

It is an *algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of order 8 embedded with a magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is composed with four equal sums magic squares of order 3. The letters M , S and T represents the magic sums of orders 3, 6 and 8, where $T = \frac{4}{3} \times S$. In order de avoid decimal entries, we must have magic sum of order 3 as multiple of 3. See below two examples:

Example 5.10. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112		pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
112	2	77	-4	-4	32	41	-58	26	112	120	5	74	-3	-4	34	42	-53	25	120
112	-1	11	17	14	17	17	8	29	112	120	1	11	18	16	17	18	10	29	120
112	-4	17	14	11	5	14	23	32	112	120	-2	20	15	10	8	15	22	32	120
112	-7	14	11	17	20	11	11	35	112	120	-5	14	12	19	20	12	13	35	120
112	35	23	50	-31	50	-10	2	-7	112	120	35	23	51	-29	50	-9	4	-5	120
112	-10	-40	14	68	-34	14	62	38	112	120	-8	-37	15	67	-31	15	61	38	120
112	95	59	-22	5	26	38	-22	-67	112	120	89	59	-21	7	26	39	-20	-59	120
	2	-49	32	32	-4	-13	86	26	112		5	-44	33	34	-4	-12	83	25	120
	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112	112		120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

The the respective magic sums for the first example for the magic squares of orders 3, 6 and 8 are given as 42, 84 and 112 respectively. For the second example the respective magic sums for the orders 3, 6 and 8 are given as 45, 90 and 120.

Result 5.11. *Let's consider following pandiagonal square of order 8 with reduced entries:*

$3*M-(3/2)*S-A2$	$3*S-2*A2-(5/2)*M+4*A1-A4-A9-A8$	$(1/3)*S-A9$	$2*A9+2*A8+(5/3)*S+4*A2+A10-2*M-(11/2)*A1-A11+A4+A3$	$M+A11-(1/2)*S$	$(1/3)*S-A10$	$(5/2)*A1-A4-A8-(13/6)*S$	$(1/6)*S-A2+(1/2)*M-A1+A4-A3$
$(3/2)*A1-(3/2)*S-A2-M$	A1	$(1/3)*S-A1+(1/2)*M-A5$	$(1/2)*M+A5-A3-(1/3)*S$	A3	$(5/6)*S-(3/2)*M+A7+A1$	$(1/6)*S+(1/2)*M-A1-A7$	$A2+(11/6)*S+M-(3/2)*A1$
$(11/6)*S+2*A9+A8+3*A2-M-(13/2)*A1+A4$	A5	$(1/3)*S-(1/2)*M$	A4	$(3/2)*M-(1/3)*S-A4-A5$	$(1/3)*S-4*A2-A10+(11/2)*A1-A4-A3-2*A9-2*A8-A7$	$2*A9+2*A8+A7+(2/3)*S+4*A2+A10-M-(11/2)*A1+A4+A3$	$M+(13/2)*A1-A4-2*A9-A8-(3/2)*S-3*A2$
$(3/2)*S-4*A2-A10-(5/2)*M+(13/2)*A1+A11-A4-A3-2*A9-2*A8$	A2+A3-A5	A1+A2-A4	$(3/2)*M-A1-(1/3)*S-A2$	$(1/3)*S-A2-(1/2)*M+A4+A5-A3$	$A9+S+A2+A10-(5/2)*M+A3$	$(3/2)*M-A3-A9-A2-A10$	$2*A9+2*A8-(7/6)*S+4*A2+A10+(5/2)*M-(13/2)*A1+A4-A11+A3$
$(1/3)*S-A11$	M-A1-A2-A3	$A4-A2-(2/3)*S+M+A5$	$A1+A2+A3+(2/3)*S-M-A4-A5$	A2	$A9+2*A8-(1/6)*S+3*A2+2*M-(13/2)*A1+A4$	$(7/6)*S-3*A2-3*M+(13/2)*A1-A4-A9-2*A8$	A11
$A2+A10+(1/2)*M-(2/3)*S$	S-M-A7	$2*A9+2*A8-(1/2)*S+4*A2+A10+M-(11/2)*A1+A4+A3+A7$	$(1/2)*S-4*A2-A10-M+(11/2)*A1-A4-A3-2*A9-A8$	S-M-A8	$(S-M)/2$	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$S-A2-A10-(1/2)*M$
$(7/6)*S+A2+A8+(3/2)*M-(5/2)*A1+A4$	A7	$(3/2)*S-4*A2-A10-2*M+(11/2)*A1-A4-A3-2*A9-2*A8-A7$	$2*A9+A8+(1/2)*S+4*A2+A10-(11/2)*A1+A4+A3$	A8	$(5*M-3*S)/2$	$(S-M)/2$	$(5/2)*A1-A4-A8-(5/6)*S-A2-(3/2)*M$
$(1/6)*S+A2-(1/2)*M+A1-A4+A3$	A9- $(8/3)*S+2*A2+A8+(5/2)*M-4*A1+A4$	A9	$2*M+(11/2)*A1-2*A9-2*A8-4*A2-A10-A4+A11-A3-(4/3)*S$	$(5/6)*S-M-A11$	A10	$(5/2)*S+A8-(5/2)*A1+A4$	$A2+(11/6)*S-3*M$

Details:

It is an **algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 embedded with a **cornered** magic square of order 6. This magic square of order 6 is again a **cornered** magic square having magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. The letters M, S and T represents the magic sums of orders 4, 6 and 8, where $T = \frac{4}{3} \times S$. In order de avoid decimal entries, we must have magic sums of orders 4 and 6 as multiples of 2 and 6 respectively. In this case, only the magic square of order 8 is **pandiagonal**, while the orders 4 and 6 are just magic squares. See below two examples:

Example 5.11. *Let's consider following two examples representing pandiagonal magic squares of order 8.*

	pan	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128		pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120
128	-80	156	-3	266	19	-6	-230	6	128	120	-59	128	-5	248	26	-8	-217	7	120
128	-166	12	10	-13	17	82	-12	198	128	120	-161	12	10	-9	17	71	-11	191	120
128	236	23	19	20	-36	-196	266	-204	128	120	221	23	15	20	-28	-198	258	-191	120
128	-67	8	6	-19	31	135	-65	99	128	120	-86	8	6	-11	27	119	-59	116	120
128	-9	-17	-9	38	14	119	-49	41	128	120	-11	-13	-1	30	14	128	-68	41	120
128	1	41	206	-145	38	35	-79	31	128	120	7	31	213	-152	28	30	-60	23	120
128	187	29	-136	215	32	-79	35	-155	128	120	186	29	-153	212	32	-60	30	-156	120
	26	-124	35	-234	13	38	262	112	128		23	-98	35	-218	4	38	247	89	120
	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128	128		120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120

The the respective magic sums for the first example for the magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8 are given as 26, 96 and 128 respectively. For the second example the respective magic sums for the orders 4, 6 and 8 are given as 30, 90 and 120. The magic rectangle sums are 70×140 for the first example and 60×120 for the second example.

Result 5.12. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

$(1/4)*M$	A_6	$A_4+2*A_3+2*A_1+A_8+2*A_5-2*M$	$A_8+A_7+A_5-(1/2)*M$	$3*M-2*A_1-A_4-2*A_3-2*A_8-A_7-2*A_5$	$(1/2)*M-A_5$	$(1/2)*M-A_6$	$(1/4)*M$
$(1/2)*M-A_6$	$(1/4)*M$	$3*M-2*A_5-2*A_1-2*A_8-2*A_3-2*A_4$	$A_5+A_1+A_8+A_3+A_4-(5/4)*M$	$A_3+A_1-(1/4)*M$	$A_5+A_8+A_4-(1/2)*M$	$(1/4)*M$	A_6
$(9/4)*M-A_4-2*A_3-A_1-A_8-2*A_5$	$A_1-(9/4)*M+2*A_5+2*A_8+2*A_3+2*A_4$	A_1	A_2	$(5/2)*M-A_5-A_2-A_8-2*A_3-A_4-2*A_1$	$A_1-(3/2)*M+A_5+A_8+2*A_3+A_4$	$(11/4)*M-A_1-2*A_5-2*A_8-2*A_3-2*A_4$	$A_4+2*A_3+A_1+A_8+2*A_5-(7/4)*M$
$(1/2)*M-A_7$	$(9/4)*M-A_1-A_3-A_4-2*A_5-2*A_8$	$(1/4)*M+A_5-A_2-A_1+A_8$	$(3/4)*M-A_5-A_8$	$2*A_1-(9/4)*M+2*A_5+2*A_8+2*A_3+A_4$	$(9/4)*M-A_1-2*A_5+A_2-2*A_8-2*A_3-A_4$	$A_1+A_3+A_4-(7/4)*M+2*A_5+2*A_8$	A_7
$A_4+2*A_3+A_1+2*A_8+A_7+2*A_5-(9/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A_3$	$2*A_1-2*M+A_5+A_2+A_8+2*A_3+A_4$	$2*M-A_5-A_1-A_8-2*A_3-A_4$	$M/2-A_1$	$M/2-A_2$	A_3	$(11/4)*M-A_4-2*A_3-A_1-2*A_8-A_7-2*A_5$
$(1/2)*M-A_8$	$(1/2)*M-A_4$	$(11/4)*M-2*A_1-2*A_5-2*A_8-2*A_3-A_4$	$A_1-(7/4)*M+2*A_5+2*A_8+2*A_3+A_4-A_2$	$(1/4)*M-A_5+A_2+A_1-A_8$	$A_5+A_8-(1/4)*M$	A_4	A_8
A_6	$(1/4)*M$	$2*A_5+2*A_1+2*A_8+2*A_3+2*A_4-(5/2)*M$	$(7/4)*M-A_5-A_1-A_8-A_3-A_4$	$(3/4)*M-A_3-A_1$	$M-A_5-A_8-A_4$	$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A_6$
$(1/4)*M$	$(1/2)*M-A_6$	$(5/2)*M-A_4-2*A_3-2*A_1-A_8-2*A_5$	$M-A_8-A_7-A_5$	$2*A_1+A_4+2*A_3+2*A_8+A_7+2*A_5-(5/2)*M$	A_5	A_6	$(1/4)*M$

Details:

It is an *algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of orders 8 and having *pandiagonal* magic square of order 4 as inner block. The letters M, S and T represents the magic sums of orders 4, 6 and 8 with $T = \frac{4}{3} \times S$ and $S = \frac{3}{2} \times M$. This means that the magic sum of order 8 depends on the choice of magic square of order 4, i.e., $T = 2 \times M$. To avoid decimal entries the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4. In this case, all the three magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.12. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

	pan	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64		pan	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72
64	8	26	90	68	-119	-7	-10	8	64	72	9	26	82	66	-107	-5	-8	9	72
64	-10	8	-110	63	20	59	8	26	64	72	-8	9	-98	58	19	57	9	26	72
64	-71	123	11	14	-65	72	-107	87	64	72	-62	114	11	14	-55	66	-96	80	72
64	-13	-86	38	-31	114	-89	102	29	64	72	-11	-77	39	-28	105	-80	95	29	72
64	132	-1	81	-56	5	2	17	-116	64	72	123	1	73	-48	7	4	17	-105	72
64	-16	-4	-98	105	-22	47	20	32	64	72	-14	-2	-87	98	-21	46	20	32	72
64	26	8	126	-47	-4	-43	8	-10	64	72	26	9	116	-40	-1	-39	9	-8	72
	8	-10	-74	-52	135	23	26	8	64		9	-8	-64	-48	125	23	26	9	72
	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64	64		72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72	72

The magic sums of first example of orders 4, 6 and 8 are 32, 48 and 64 respectively. The magic sums of orders 4, 6, and 8 are 36, 54 and 72 respectively.

Result 5.13. Let's consider following *pandiagonal* square of order 8 with reduced entries:

$m/2$	$A_6 - (9/10)m + A_2 + A_1 - A_5 + A_7$	$m - A_6$	$(12/5)m - A_2 - A_1 - A_3 - A_4$	$A_3 + A_4 + A_1 - m$	$(1/2)m - A_1 + A_5$	$m - A_7$	$m/2$
$A_1 - A_6 + A_3 + A_5 - A_7$	$(12/5)m - A_2 - 2A_1 - A_3$	A_1	$(3/5)m$	A_2	$(1/2)m + A_6 - A_5$	$A_1 + A_3 + A_5 - (1/2)m - A_6$	$m + A_6 - A_1 - A_3 - A_5 + A_7$
$(1/2)m + A_6 - A_1$	$2A_1 - (7/5)m + A_3 + A_2$	$m - A_1$	$(2/5)m$	$m - A_2$	$(1/2)m - A_6 + A_5$	$(3/2)m + A_6 - A_1 - A_3 - A_5$	$(1/2)m - A_6 + A_1$
A_4	$(9/10)m - A_1$	$(3/2)m - A_3 - A_2$	$A_3 + A_2 + A_1 - (9/10)m$	$(3/2)m - A_3 - A_1$	$A_3 - m + A_6 + A_1 - A_5 + A_2$	$m - A_2 - A_6 + A_5$	$m - A_4$
$m - A_4$	$(1/10)m + A_1$	$A_3 + A_2 - (1/2)m$	$(19/10)m - A_3 - A_2 - A_1$	$A_3 + A_1 - (1/2)m$	$2m - A_3 - A_2 - A_1 - A_6 + A_5$	$A_2 + A_6 - A_5$	A_4
$m - A_5$	$(19/10)m - A_6 - A_1 - A_3 + A_5 - A_2$	$(1/2)m + A_6 - A_5$	$(1/10)m - A_6 + A_1 + A_5$	$A_2 + (1/2)m + A_6 - A_1 - A_5$	A_1	A_3	A_5
$(1/2)m + A_7 - A_3$	$A_3 + A_2 + A_1 - (9/10)m + A_6 - A_5$	$(1/2)m - A_6 + A_5$	$(9/10)m + A_6 - A_1 - A_5$	$(1/2)m - A_2 - A_6 + A_1 + A_5$	$m - A_1$	$m - A_3$	$(1/2)m + A_3 - A_7$
$m/2$	$(19/10)m - A_6 - A_2 - A_1 + A_5 - A_7$	A_6	$A_2 + A_1 + A_3 - (7/5)m + A_4$	$2m - A_3 - A_4 - A_1$	$(1/2)m + A_1 - A_5$	A_7	$m/2$

Details:

It is an *algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal* magic square of orders 8 and having *pandiagonal* magic square of order 6 in the inner block. It is composed of three equal sums magic rectangles of order $m \times 3m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangle. The letters S and T represents the magic sums of orders 6 and 8 with the condition $T = \frac{4}{3} \times S$. To avoid decimal entries the width of magic rectangle of order $m \times 3m$ should be multiple of 10. In this case, all the magic squares of orders 6 and 8 are *pandiagonal*. See below two examples:

Example 5.13. Let's consider following two examples representing *pandiagonal* magic squares of order 8.

8x8	pan	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	8x8	pan	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160
120	15	30	4	10	18	27	1	15	120	160	20	21	14	34	8	32	11	20	160
120	-4	19	11	18	14	18	10	34	120	160	-4	43	11	24	14	23	5	44	160
120	30	11	19	12	16	12	20	0	120	160	35	-3	29	16	26	17	35	5	160
120	20	16	14	15	17	15	13	10	120	160	20	25	29	6	32	5	23	20	160
120	10	14	16	15	13	15	17	20	120	160	20	15	11	34	8	35	17	20	160
120	7	12	18	11	21	11	17	23	120	160	17	31	23	12	26	11	17	23	160
120	27	18	12	19	9	19	13	3	120	160	32	9	17	28	14	29	23	8	160
	15	0	26	20	12	3	29	15	120		20	19	26	6	32	8	29	20	160
	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120	120		160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160	160

The magic sums of first example of orders 6 and 8 are 90 and 120, and for the second example are 120 and 160 respectively.

5.6 Summary

In this section, there are 10 results on **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 8. Each result is of different type of nature. These results are summarizing below along with conditions to avoid **decimal** or **fractional** entries:

1. **Result 5.1:** It is an **algebraic pandiagonal** magic square composed of 4 equal sums **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4. It requires magic sum of order 4 as multiple of 2.
2. **Result 5.2:** It is an **algebraic pandiagonal** magic square formed by 8 equal sums **strips** (magic rectangles) of order 2×4 . Moreover, it is formed by five equal sums magic squares of order 4. In this case there are no conditions on magic sum but due to **magic rectangles**, the final magic sum of order 8 is always an even number.
3. **Result 5.3:** It is an **algebraic double-digit pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 having a magic squares of order 4 in the middle. In this case, the magic sum of order 4 should be even number. Secondly, the first entries, i.e., A1 and A2 should also be even numbers.
4. **Result 5.4:** It is an **algebraic cornered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 having a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic sum of order 6 should be multiple of 6.
5. **Result 5.5:** It is an **algebraic cornered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8, where orders 4 and 6 are just magic squares. In this case the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 6.
6. **Result 5.6:** It is an **algebraic cornered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 6 at the upper-left corner composed with four equal sums **semi-magic** squares of order 3. In this case, the **semi-magic** sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3.
7. **Result 5.7:** It is an **algebraic cornered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 having again a **single-digit bordered pandiagonal** of order 6 at the upper-left corner. with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. This means, all the three magic squares of orders 4, 6 and 8 are **pandiagonal**. It requires the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4.
8. **Result 5.8:** It is an **algebraic cornered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 having again a **striped pandiagonal** of order 6 at the upper-left corner with three magic rectangles of order $m \times 3m$, where m is the width of the magic rectangle. The magic squares of orders 6 and 8 are

- pandiagonal.** It requires that the width of the magic rectangle in the magic square of order 6 should be multiple of 10.
9. **Result 5.9:** It is an **algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 having **pandiagonal** magic square of order 6 in the middle. In this case, the magic sum of order 6 should be multiple of 6.
 10. **Result 5.10:** It is an **algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 having magic square of order 6 in the middle. This magic square of order 6 is composed with four equal sums magic squares of order 3. In this case, the magic sum of order 3 should be multiple of 3.
 11. **Result 5.11:** It is an **algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 having magic square of order 6 in the middle. It is an **algebraic cornered** This magic square of order 6 with magic square of order 4 at the upper-left corner. In this case, the magic sums of orders 4 and 6 should be multiples of 2 and 6 respectively.
 12. **Result 5.12:** It is an **algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 having again a **single-digit bordered pandiagonal** of order 6 with **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4 in the middle. In this case the magic sum of order 4 should be multiple of 4.
 13. **Result 5.13:** It is an **algebraic single-digit bordered pandiagonal** magic square of order 8 having again a **striped pandiagonal** magic square of order 6 in the middle. In this case the width of magic rectangle should multiple of 10.

6 Author's Contribution to Magic Squares and Recreation Numbers

For author's contribution to **magic squares** and **recreation numbers** lease see the links below:

- **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-magic-squares/>
- **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers,
 - (i) <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>
 - (ii) <https://inderjtaneja.wordpress.com/2019/06/27/publications-recreation-of-numbers/>

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